

Evidence and Gap Map of evidence syntheses on sex- and gender-specific health and health care: a scoping review protocol

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This protocol is adapted from the *Joanna Briggs Institute* template for scoping review protocols.

1. Introduction

This scoping review will inform the project: *Artificial Intelligence to Expedite Sex/Gender Analysis in Evidence Synthesis: a use case of Digital Health Interventions for Cancer Patients*¹. This is a three-year project funded by the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF) under the National Research Programme (NRP) 83 “Gender Medicine and Health”² (project number 408340_227036).

The general aim of this scoping review is to identify and characterise evidence syntheses that specifically examine how sex, gender, gender identity, gender modality, and sexual orientation are associated with health conditions and health care outcomes. The review will also tackle intersectionality of sex and gender with other equity dimensions, that is, age, ethnicity/race, socioeconomic position, geography, language/religion, disability, and underrepresented groups.

The scoping review will focus on evidence syntheses published from 1 January 2017 onwards, following publication of the Sex and Gender Equity in Research (SAGER) guidelines in 2016.³

2. Objectives of the scoping review

The scoping review will have the following specific objectives.

Objective 1. To describe sex and gender terms and concepts used in evidence syntheses on sex- and gender-specific health and health care.

Objective 2. To describe how the included evidence syntheses consider intersectionality of sex and gender with other equity dimensions.

Objective 3. To develop an online Evidence and Gap Map (EGM) of evidence syntheses on sex- and gender-specific health and health care. The online, interactive, and freely accessible EGM will present the included evidence syntheses according to factors relevant to interest-holders, such as the presence of differences by sex or gender.

3. Eligibility criteria

The review eligibility criteria will follow the PCC (population, concept, context) format⁴.

3.1. Population (P)

Eligible evidence syntheses must address topics related to human health, health conditions, or health care processes. In this review, the population criterion refers to the human populations, health-related conditions, health care processes, or health system contexts addressed by the included evidence syntheses.

Eligible topics may address any stage of the health or disease continuum, including health promotion, prevention, diagnosis, treatment, rehabilitation, palliative care, health care access, quality of care, patient safety, health care delivery, and health system organisation. Any health care discipline or setting (in-person or virtual) will be eligible. Any research with a clear connection to human health outcomes or health care delivery will be eligible. For example, an evidence synthesis evaluating the safety of seat belts in female drivers compared to male drivers would be eligible because of its relevance to injury prevention and human safety. We will exclude research without human participants or human data, such as preclinical research in animals or cellular research. Evidence syntheses including both human and non-human evidence will be eligible.

3.2. Concept (C)

3.2.1. Topic that the scoping review will explore

This scoping review will include research that explicitly addresses sex, gender, gender identity, gender modality or sexual orientation in relation to health conditions or health care. The concept of interest will be how these factors are examined as sources of differences in health outcomes, health care access, delivery, quality, safety, or effectiveness. Thus, the included evidence syntheses should have sex, gender, gender identity, gender modality, or sexual orientation as a central component of the review question or objectives.

Evidence syntheses focused on engineering, technology, digital tools, medical devices, diagnostics, clinical algorithms, or datasets used for clinical prediction will be eligible when they have a clear link to a health condition, health outcome, or a health care process. For example, the evaluation of woman-controlled HIV prevention methods designed to support women in contexts

where they may have limited power to refuse sex or cannot rely on partners to use condoms⁵ will be eligible.

3.2.2. Definitions and terminology

Appendix 1 defines sex, gender identity, gender modality and sexual orientation concepts. These definitions are based on different sources, particularly the SAGER guidelines³, Rioux *et al*⁶, the SWISS LGBTIQ+ Panel 2025⁷, and the EQUALSS GUIDE Multiple framework for equity-focused SRs⁸. If additional terms are found, we will consult their definition in other sources, such as the LGBTIQ+ glossary developed by The Equality Network in Scotland⁹. We aim to use inclusive language as it supports diversity and conveys respect¹⁰. However, we acknowledge that this is an ongoing process and remain committed to continuous learning and reflection as our project evolves.

3.2.3. Consideration of intersectionality

This scoping review will examine intersectionality as a descriptive and analytic dimension of included research, rather than as a mandatory inclusion criterion. Intersectionality is understood here as the interaction of sex, gender, gender identity, gender modality or sexual orientation with other equity factors that may jointly shape health and health care outcomes. See Appendix 2 for definitions of intersectionality factors.

Health inequalities refer to measurable differences in health outcomes between population groups, whereas **health inequities** denote those differences, that is, inequalities, that are unnecessary and avoidable and, in addition, are considered unfair and unjust¹¹. **Health equity** (equity in health) is defined as the absence of **health inequities**, is achieved when all individuals have a fair opportunity to attain their full health potential, and no one is disadvantaged from achieving this potential due to socially determined circumstances¹².

To describe a certain situation as inequitable, its cause must be examined and judged to be unfair in the context of broader societal conditions¹¹. In general, health differences among socially determined groups are considered avoidable, unnecessary, and unfair. Examples include groups defined by economic status, demographic characteristics, geography, gender, ethnicity, disability, or sexual orientation¹³.

Research will be eligible if it meets the core concept criteria (i.e., explicitly addresses sex, gender, gender identity, gender modality or sexual orientation in relation to health conditions or health

care). Thus, research will **not** be excluded solely because it does not address additional intersectionality factors. However, research focusing on equity dimensions such as ethnicity or socioeconomic position, without explicit consideration of sex, gender, gender identity, gender modality or sexual orientation, will be excluded. For example, research assessing differences in access to screening services based on ethnic groups will be excluded, whereas research on gender differences in access to screening services within minority ethnic groups will be eligible. Another example of eligible research would be a systematic review assessing the unique health care needs of older LGBTQ+ individuals⁸.

Evidence syntheses on sex-related or reproductive health conditions, such as prostate cancer or pregnancy, will be eligible only if they explicitly examine gender, gender identity, gender modality, or sexual orientation as a substantive dimension of the review question, analysis, interpretation, or synthesis. For example, a systematic review comparing outcomes among people with prostate cancer according to sexual orientation would be eligible.

3.2.4. Classification of research questions in sex- and gender-specific health

The scoping review will classify research questions on sex- and gender-specific health in three phases (see Appendix 3). The classification is adapted from Peters et al.'s roadmap, the EQUALSS GUIDE Multiple framework for equity-focused SRs, and other sources^{8,14-17}.

Phase 1 (exploration) explores, identifies or quantifies the presence or absence of sex/gender differences in health. Research at this phase is mainly descriptive, cataloguing differences without explaining why they exist.

Phase 2 (explanation) moves from identifying sex and gender differences to explaining them, that is, uncovering their underlying causes. Understanding these reasons is critical to determine what can be done to address them. This phase requires evidence on causal pathways.

Phase 3 (translation to policy and practice) includes research evaluating the effects of interventions to address sex and gender differences¹⁸.

3.3. Context (C)

Eligible evidence syntheses may address any health care setting, care delivery environment, health-related context, or geographical location. Settings will include any environment in which health care, public health, prevention, diagnosis, treatment, rehabilitation, long-term care, or palliative care is delivered or studied, whether in person, remotely, or virtually.

We will consider all health care disciplines, spanning the continuum from primary prevention (measures to prevent disease or injury before it occurs in healthy individuals) to palliative care (prevention and relief of health-related suffering among adults, children, and their families facing problems associated with life-threatening illness)¹⁹.

Engineering or technology-focused research (e.g., diagnostics, medical devices, digital tools, clinical algorithms, datasets used for clinical prediction) will be eligible if it assesses evidence in humans and is clearly linked to a health condition or health care process.

Meta-research (research on research), as well as research on AI methods in health or health care, will be eligible.

3.4. Types of evidence sources

3.4.1. Evidence syntheses

The scoping review will include evidence syntheses.

Evidence synthesis is “a broad term referring to different types of reviews that systematically compile and analyse information from multiple documents such as studies or reports on a similar topic to develop an overall understanding of the results”²⁰. Evidence synthesis combines information from a variety of sources using explicit and transparent methodologies, to inform decision-making on specific issues²¹.

We will include any evidence synthesis type as listed as part of the *Evidence Synthesis Family* in Nussbaumer-Streit et al²⁰. We plan to collaborate with the *Evidence Synthesis Taxonomy Initiative* (ESTI)²² and the classification/terminology of eligible evidence syntheses may be modified. See Appendix 4 for the eligible evidence synthesis types.

3.4.1.1. Inclusion criteria of evidence syntheses

The evidence synthesis should meet **all** of the following criteria:

- 1. Clearly stated review objective or question.**
- 2. Defined eligibility criteria**, including a description of the main components of the review question, such as population, intervention/exposure, comparator, outcomes, context, phenomenon of interest, or other relevant elements, depending on the review type.
- 3. Systematic search methods, evidenced by:**

- a. search in at least one electronic database (e.g., MEDLINE, Embase, CINAHL, PsycINFO, Scopus, Web of Science, CENTRAL) or subject-specific database; and
 - b. reporting sufficient information to understand how the search was conducted (e.g., database name(s) and key search concepts/terms). Note: reporting the full search strategy and the time frame are desirable but not required for eligibility.
4. **Explicit study selection process**, including a description of how records, studies, reports, or other evidence sources were selected for inclusion, even if reported briefly.
 5. **Synthesis of included evidence**: description of the methods used to combine, summarise, map, or interpret the findings (e.g., narrative synthesis, meta-analysis, thematic synthesis, framework synthesis, realist synthesis, evidence mapping).

These criteria are intended to distinguish evidence syntheses using systematic and transparent methods from purely narrative, traditional, or opinion-based reviews.

3.4.1.2. Methodological features recorded but not used as eligibility criteria

The following methodological features will be extracted, when reported, but will not be used to determine eligibility: 1) Presence of an a priori review protocol and whether it was registered/published (e.g., PROSPERO, OSF); 2) Whether dual independent processes were used for screening, data extraction, or critical appraisal; 3) Whether a critical appraisal/risk of bias assessment was conducted; 4) Whether certainty of evidence was assessed (e.g., GRADE, GRADE-CERQual)^{23 24}; and 5) Whether meta-analysis or another quantitative synthesis was performed.

3.4.1.3. Exclusions

We will exclude the following publication types.

- Reviews explicitly described as narrative reviews, literature reviews, traditional reviews, or non-systematic reviews
- Reviews that did not search at least one electronic bibliographic database or subject-specific database/index.
- Reviews for which it is not possible to determine whether at least one electronic bibliographic database or subject-specific database/index was searched. Authors will not be contacted for clarification; these records will be excluded because of insufficient reporting of search methods.

3.4.2. Evidence synthesis conduct

We will include evidence syntheses conducted in standard, rapid, or living review mode. The mode of conduct will be recorded during data extraction, when reported, but will not be used as an eligibility criterion.

For the purposes of this review, evidence syntheses will be classified according to how the review process was conducted and maintained: standard evidence syntheses; rapid evidence syntheses; and living evidence syntheses.

3.4.2.1. Standard evidence synthesis

Standard evidence synthesis methodology follows a highly structured, transparent and reproducible approach. To ensure methodological rigour and minimise bias, key steps, such as assessing identified records for eligibility (screening) and extracting data, are normally conducted independently by at least two reviewers. This process comprises the following phases:

- Study selection
- Data extraction: data from included studies are extracted for further analysis
- Data analysis and synthesis
- Critical appraisal or assessment of methodological limitations, where appropriate for the review type
- Assessment of the certainty of the evidence (where applicable): evaluation of confidence in the overall body of evidence using established frameworks such as *Grading of Recommendations, Assessment, Development, and Evaluation* [GRADE]²³ and *Confidence in Evidence from Reviews of Qualitative research* [GRADE-CERQual]²⁴.

3.4.2.2. Rapid review mode

Rapid reviews are evidence syntheses that accelerate the review process by simplifying or omitting certain methodological steps, while explicitly reporting any methodological shortcuts^{20, 25}. Examples include conducting study selection or data extraction by a single reviewer and limiting the number of databases searched. A rapid approach can be applied across different types of evidence syntheses.

3.4.2.3. Living review mode

Living evidence syntheses are reviews continuously updated by regularly searching for new evidence, rapidly incorporating relevant findings, and providing timely updates²⁶. A living

evidence synthesis requires clear, predefined plans for search frequency and the process of integrating new evidence²⁷. A living review mode can be applied to any evidence synthesis type.

3.4.3. Evidence synthesis format

We will include completed evidence syntheses published in English in peer-reviewed journals from 1 January 2017 onwards. This date was selected to reflect the publication of the SAGER guidelines in 2016. We acknowledge that these criteria may introduce bias by excluding non-English and non-journal evidence, which may be relevant in equity and LGBTQ+ health research.

Evidence syntheses only available in the following formats will be excluded.

1. Preprints
2. Withdrawn or retracted reviews
3. Reviews exclusively published as an abstract, such as conference abstracts
4. Books or book chapters
5. Clinical practice guidelines (evidence syntheses supporting guidelines will be eligible if they are published separately as a peer-reviewed article)
6. Master or doctoral dissertations
7. Registrations or protocols, such as those registered in PROSPERO or published as a protocol in a peer-reviewed journal. They will be excluded but listed in an appendix if they meet the remaining inclusion criteria.

4. Methods

4.1. Study design

This scoping review will follow the *Joanna Briggs Institute* (JBI) guidance²⁸. The final manuscript will be reported according to the *Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses Extension for Scoping Reviews* (PRISMA-ScR)²⁹. There are multiple definitions for scoping review. In this project, we will adopt the PRISMA-ScR definition, which describes a scoping review as a form of knowledge synthesis that follows a systematic approach to map evidence on a topic and identify main concepts, theories, sources, and knowledge gaps²⁹.

This protocol was deposited on Zenodo (8 May 2026). Any amendments to, or deviations from the protocol will be documented and justified in the final review report.

4.2. Interest-holders engagement

This scoping review is guided by a commitment to representing the views of interest-holders, defined as individuals or groups with a legitimate interest in the health issue under consideration. We will engage both academic and non-academic partners throughout the review process. We define “involvement” as any contribution by interest-holders to the development of the review protocol, the conduct of any stage of the review, or the dissemination of findings³⁰. Engaging interest-holders in evidence synthesis offers several benefits, including reducing research waste by enhancing relevance to affected populations, increasing transparency and rigour, and improving the dissemination of findings^{31,32}. This review will follow the JBI's guidance for interest-holders' engagement in scoping reviews³¹, based on the ACTIVE framework³³.

We will adopt a combined engagement approach, incorporating both one-time and ongoing involvement, with direct collaboration between researchers and interest-holders to inform key stages of the review.

As part of the project planning stage, we have created an advisory group using a purposive sampling strategy³⁴ to include key interest-holders involved in the development and use of evidence synthesis. The advisory board will contribute to the scoping review as follows: a) check that the inclusion criteria and the language are inclusive; b) check that all the relevant terms are included in the search strategies; c) suggest sources to find evidence syntheses; d) check that the data extraction form does not miss critical concepts; e) identify overlap with other initiatives.

Moreover, we will engage other interest-holders, such as patients and professionals working in SNSF-funded projects under the National Research Programme (NRP) 83 “Gender Medicine and Health”². The interest-holders will contribute from an early stage to choose which characteristics of the evidence syntheses will be displayed in the EGM.

Interest-holders will not receive financial compensation for their contributions. Contributors who meet the *International Committee of Medical Journal Editors'* authorship criteria will be invited to be co-authors of the final manuscripts. Contributions from those who do not meet authorship criteria will be acknowledged in the reports, with their permission.

4.3. Search methods

We will search in MEDLINE (via PubMed) and Epistemonikos for evidence syntheses published in

English since 1 January 2017 to the date of the search. An experienced health sciences information specialist (DBG) will design the search strategies. A second information specialist (CCA) will peer review the search strategies using the PRESS checklist.³⁵ The strategies will combine controlled vocabulary terms, where available, and free-text terms related to evidence syntheses, health, sex, gender, gender identity, gender modality, and sexual orientation. Search filters for identifying relevant articles will be considered and adapted to each database interface where applicable. The draft search strategy is provided in Appendix 5. The final search strategies for all databases, including search dates and any limits applied, will be reported in the final review manuscript.

4.4. Study selection

We will collate all identified citations into *EndNote* 2025 (Clarivate Analytics, PA, USA) and remove duplicates. Following deduplication, we will import the citation details of the unique records into *EPPI-Reviewer* software³⁶ to implement the selection process. Study selection will be conducted in accordance with the predefined eligibility criteria and will involve two phases: 1) titles/abstracts screening and 2) full-text assessment. We will pilot the selection process with a sample of 200 records. The team will discuss discrepancies and modify the decision categories if needed. The results of the searches and the selection process will be described in the final report and presented in a PRISMA 2020 flow diagram³⁷.

To be eligible, research must report in the title or abstract that the consideration of sex, gender (including gender identity or gender modality), or sexual orientation (e.g., “to assess sex differences...”, “gender-specific...”, “LGBTQ+ populations...”) plays a relevant role in the study. Therefore, the title or abstract must demonstrate an intent to examine sex, gender, gender identity, gender modality or sexual orientation by at least one of the following factors:

1. Eligibility criteria that restrict or define populations based on these concepts (e.g., women-only with a rationale related to gender; transgender populations; sexual minority groups; intersex populations).
2. Conceptual or analytical frameworks indicating that sex, gender, gender identity, gender modality or sexual orientation are integral to the synthesis (e.g., explicit use of sex- and gender-based analysis approaches, subgroup analyses, stratified syntheses, meta-regression, intersectionality frameworks, or equity-focused synthesis frameworks).

We acknowledge that this approach may fail to identify relevant information, as abstracts do not always report sex, gender, or sexual orientation, often due to word limits or journal formatting constraints. Therefore, research will be excluded if sex, gender, gender identity, gender modality or sexual orientation appear only as a post hoc or incidental stratification of results, without a clear demonstration in the abstract that it plays a relevant role in the study. For example, we will exclude reviews evaluating the effects of a health care intervention that simply report general statements as “no sex differences were found,” without indicating in the objectives or methods of the abstract that sex, gender, gender identity, gender modality or sexual orientation were planned to be evaluated.

Phase 1. Title/abstract screening

During title/abstract screening, each record will be assessed by two reviewers independently (CWA, CM, JLA or DBG). Disagreements will be resolved through discussion between the two reviewers. If disagreement cannot be solved, an additional reviewer will intervene (JLA, DBG or CMW).

Phase 2. Full-text assessment

At the full-text assessment phase, each record will be assessed independently by two reviewers (CWA, JLA, CM or DBG). Disagreements will be resolved through discussion between the two reviewers. If disagreement cannot be solved, an additional reviewer will intervene (JLA, DBG or CMW). We will not contact the study authors for clarification in case of unclear information about eligibility.

4.5. Data extraction

4.5.1. Data extraction process

We will collate multiple reports referring to the same evidence synthesis (e.g., protocol and final report; successive versions of a living review) and treat them as a single study unit. We will specify which report is the primary reference. Where key data elements are missing in the primary reference, we will consult other sources associated with the study to complete those fields. We will record the source for each completed item (such as, primary report, protocol or other report). We will not contact study authors to clarify missing or unclear information, which will be coded as “Not reported” or “Reported but unclear”.

We will use a pre-designed data extraction form in *EPPI-Reviewer*³⁶. One reviewer (CWa, CM, or DBG) will manually extract data. A second reviewer (CM, JLA, or DBG) will verify extracted data for key variables (the list of key variables will be defined during the data extraction pilot). Disagreements will be resolved by discussion; unresolved cases will be adjudicated by a third reviewer (JLA or CMW).

We will pilot the extraction form on 20–30 evidence syntheses (or until no new coding issues arise). We will finalise the form once extraction time is feasible and agreement on key variables is acceptable. The final extraction form and decision rules will be provided in the final manuscript. Draft data extraction tools are provided in Appendix 6 and Appendix 7 and may be revised following feedback from the scoping review team and other interest-holders.

4.5.2. Coding of health conditions

Health conditions will be coded using ICD-11 at the **chapter level** (and, where greater detail is needed, up to two additional levels)³⁸. For studies covering multiple conditions, we will code all applicable ICD-11 codes and additionally classify the review as “Multi-condition”. Where the condition is broad or unclear, we will code “Reported but unclear” or “Not reported” and record the authors’ terminology verbatim. If the condition is not covered by ICD-11, we will code “Other”.

4.5.3. Coding of sex, gender and sexual orientation concepts

We will extract and code sex, gender identity, gender modality, and sexual orientation as separate concepts to avoid attributing findings to sex when they may instead relate to gender or to interactions between sex and gender^{6,39}. Moreover, we will use a non-binary conceptualisation of sex and gender and will include categories such as intersex and gender-diverse populations. Definitions of relevant concepts and categories concerning sex and gender are provided in Appendix 1. We will extract and code sex, gender and sexual orientation concepts as detailed in Appendix 7.

4.5.4. Handling sex/gender terminology

Data extraction from evidence syntheses addressing sex and gender can be challenging for several reasons. First, these concepts are often not clearly defined in published papers, requiring readers to infer what the authors intended to examine^{40,41}. Second, research papers often use binary categories, such as men and women, or define sex solely based on external genitalia assessed at birth^{6,42}. Third, sex and gender are sometimes used interchangeably in the same

report, leading to inconsistencies between the concept named and the groups reported. For example, a study may initially refer to sex but use terms related to sex and gender throughout the article. Finally, terminology related to sex and gender varies across time and place and sex and gender are measured inconsistently⁶, further complicating data extraction.

We will follow the PROEDI approach to handle unclear sex/gender terminology in our data extraction process¹⁰. We will first record the definitions and terminology used by the study authors. Second, we will describe how sex and gender concepts and terms were considered, following Adisso et al.'s framework (see 4.6.1. Data analysis, and Appendix 6)⁴³. Third, we will try to convert the reported concepts and terms according to our predefined framework. For example, if an evidence synthesis clearly considered sex but used gender categories, we will record the authors' terminology verbatim as free text, reclassify the categories as sex-based, and explicitly note this conversion. If a construct or term is unclear, we will code it as "Reported but unclear" or "Not reported," provide a justification for this classification, and record the authors' terminology verbatim.

4.5.5. Coding of intersectionality

For each included evidence synthesis, we will extract whether intersectionality was considered and the specific dimensions of the "EQUALSS GUIDE Multiple" framework that were examined alongside sex/gender/sexual orientation: E (Ethnicity and Race), Q (qualifications and education), I (income and wealth), E (employment and occupation), U (underserved area), A (age), L (language & Religion), D (physical, mental and learning disabilities), U (underrepresented groups)⁸. Appendix 2 defines the factors related to intersectionality.

Additionally, we will extract the approach used to consider intersectionality (such as stratified analyses, subgroup analyses or meta-regression within minoritised populations, causal frameworks, equity frameworks, or qualitative conceptualisation).

4.5.6. Coding of the Evidence and Gap Map

The scoping review will inform the development of an EGM to display evidence syntheses according to the targets of the third Sustainable Development Goal (SDG-3): *Ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages*⁴⁴ and additional characteristics that will be agreed with the interest-holders. See draft data extraction form for the EGM in Appendix 7.

4.6. Data analysis

4.6.1. Objective 1. To describe sex and gender terms and concepts used in evidence syntheses on sex- and gender-specific health and health care

We will consider the framework developed by Adisso et al.’s⁴³ to describe sex and gender concepts and terms in the included studies, including the “non-binary use”, “use of categories” and “non-interchangeable use of sex and gender”. Adisso’s framework is based on the Canadian Institutes of Health Research (CIHR)⁴⁵, and the U.S. National Institutes of Health (NIH)⁴⁶ proposals. See decision rules in Appendix 6.

We will perform a descriptive analysis of the sex- and gender-related terms used in the evidence syntheses by using frequency counts (numbers and percentages). We will describe the following features: 1) “Non-binary use” of sex and gender; 2) “Use of categories” for sex and gender; and 3) “Non-interchangeable use” of sex and gender.

We will explore associations between criteria met and evidence synthesis characteristics that will be chosen based on the input of interest-holders, such as year of publication, region of the first author of the evidence syntheses, or health condition.

4.6.2. Objective 2. To describe how the included evidence syntheses consider intersectionality

We will perform descriptive analysis of the included evidence syntheses that considered intersectionality of sex, gender, gender identity or sexual orientation in combination with additional equity dimensions by using frequency counts (numbers and percentages).

We will report the terms used and the frequency of evidence syntheses addressing each equity dimension other than sex, gender, gender identity or sexual orientation:

1. Age
2. Ethnicity/race
3. Socioeconomic position
4. Geography
5. Language/religion
6. Disability
7. Underrepresented groups
8. Multiple disadvantage

We will explore associations between criteria met and evidence synthesis characteristics that will be chosen based on the input of interest-holders, such as year of publication or region of the first author of the evidence syntheses, or health condition.

4.6.3. Objective 3. To develop an EGM of evidence syntheses on sex- and gender-specific health and health care

We will perform a descriptive analysis of the characteristics of the evidence syntheses included in the Evidence and Gap Map by using frequency counts (numbers and percentages). For example, we will report the frequency of evidence syntheses by region, research phase, and health condition. The EGM will show differences in outcomes by sex or gender. The characteristics in the analysis will be informed by input from interest-holders concerning relevant data for interpreting the EGM. A narrative summary will accompany the EGM. Analyses and presentation of data will consider sex, gender identity, gender modality, and sexual orientation as distinct properties.

4.6.4. Statistical analysis

All data will be stored in *EPPI-Reviewer* software³⁶. Numerical outputs will be transferred into Excel (Microsoft Corp., Redmond, WA, USA) and analysed using R software⁴⁷. Associations between criteria and evidence synthesis characteristics will be examined using the Pearson chi-squared test⁴⁸ or Fisher's exact test⁴⁹, as appropriate.

4.7. Data dissemination

The findings of this scoping review and the EGM will be disseminated through several channels to maximise accessibility and impact.

4.7.1. Presentation at an international conference

The results and key findings of the scoping review and EGM will be shared with the broader scientific community via a presentation at an international conference.

4.7.2. Article in an international peer-reviewed journal

In addition, a final manuscript detailing the findings of the scoping review and the EGM will be prepared and submitted for publication in an international peer-reviewed journal.

4.7.3. Launch of the interactive EGM

We will use *EPPI-Visualiser*, *EPPI-Mapper* or a similar tool to generate an openly accessible online EGM. This platform will allow users to seamlessly explore the data through frequency and

crosstabulation charts, view the assigned coding, and directly export and save the study metadata. The EGM will be structured to display evidence syntheses according to the targets of the third Sustainable Development Goal (SDG-3: Ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages) alongside additional relevant characteristics agreed upon with our interest-holders.

4.7.4. Interest-holders' engagement in the project dissemination

The dissemination process will be collaborative, involving our established advisory group as well as other professionals working within the Swiss National Science Foundation's National Research Programme (NRP) 83 "Gender Medicine and Health". Moreover, interest-holders will be involved in assessing whether the plain language summaries and infographics associated with the Evidence and Gap Map are useful and clear. Ultimately, the disseminated data will directly inform the broader three-year project: *Artificial Intelligence to Expedite Sex/Gender Analysis in Evidence Synthesis: a use case of Digital Health Interventions for Cancer Patients*.

5. Acknowledgements

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7. Ethics

The Cantonal Ethics Committee Zurich stated that the project did not fall within the scope of the Human Research Act in Switzerland (BASEC-Nr Req-2024-00971; July 26, 2024).

8. Declarations

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

9. Author contributions

JLA, CMW, CWa, and JH conceived this scoping review. JLA, DBG and CCA designed and executed preliminary searches. JLA wrote the first draft of this protocol. All authors read the protocol critically and approved its final version. CM edited the report for language and clarity. CMW obtained funding for this scoping review. CMW is the guarantor.

10. References

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Appendix 1. Sex and gender concepts

	Subcategories	Examples
		<p>We will consider sex, gender, gender identity and sexual orientation as suggested in the SAGER guidelines³, Rioux <i>et al</i>⁶, the Swiss LGBTIQ+ Panel⁷, Canadian Institutes of Health Research⁴³, and the EQUALSS GUIDE Multiple framework for equity-focused SRs⁸. If additional terms are found, we will consult their definition in other sources, such as the LGBTI+ glossary developed by The Equality Network in Scotland⁹.</p> <p>S: sex</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ A set of biological attributes in humans and animals that are associated with physical and physiological features including chromosomes, gene expression, hormone function and reproductive/sexual anatomy³. ▪ Sex is a classification (male, female or intersex) usually assigned at birth based on visual anatomy assessment⁶. ▪ Sex is not binary. ▪ Although sex is often thought of as an exclusively biological characteristic, it is also a social construct in that it is based on an expectation of what bodies should look like.^{50, 51} <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding of sex may vary between countries and cultures. • Sex differences are thought to stem from genetic, epigenetic, hormonal, and/or physiological factors, and usually examined in terms of different biological systems leading to differences in disease susceptibility and manifestation.⁵² However, sex features are not perfectly correlated and can change across time, with no boundary or biological marker clearly delineating ‘male’ and ‘female’ sexes.^{53, 54} • While sex assigned at birth may be used in epidemiological cohort studies as a proxy of biological systems, the limitations of this measure in terms of correspondence with genitalia, organs, genetics and hormones should be acknowledged. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 3G-sex (Genetics, Gonadal sex and Genitalia) are dimorphic and consistent, characteristics commonly associated with sex. ○ However, hormones, brain systems and anatomy other than genitalia (e.g., breasts, facial/body hair), are not dimorphic or internally consistent.⁵⁵ ▪ The Endocrine Society Clinical Practice Guidelines recommend that the term ‘biological’ sex be avoided.⁵⁶
	Male	
	Female	
	Intersex	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ A person whose sex characteristics (e.g., chromosomes, gonads, hormones, or external/internal reproductive organs) do not align with typical binary notions of male or female bodies. ▪ One of the classifications typically assigned at birth based on visual genital inspection. ▪ The term challenges the belief that sex is strictly binary and highlights biological diversity. ▪ Other descriptions of intersex might be found and if so, we will report them, such as person with differences of sex development (DSD), ‘Not specified’, ‘Would prefer not to respond’.
		<p>G: Gender</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The socially constructed roles, behaviours and identities of female, male and gender diverse people³ ▪ Gender is a social configuration that gathers the roles, behaviour, activities, feelings, attitudes and attributes that a given society typically associates with being masculine or feminine⁶. ▪ Gender differences stem from power structures, social position, inequalities and restrictive behavioural norms influencing patterns of risk exposure, health behaviours, care access and other pathways to health and well-being.⁵⁷

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Gender is not binary. ▪ Understanding of gender may vary across the world. ▪ Avoid using ‘non-binary’ as a catch all category if possible, as some experience this practice as harmful⁵⁸. ▪ When ‘boys’ and ‘girls’ are used for children, it should be listed as ‘gender’ and include other gender identities. 		
	Man	
	Woman	
	Other gender identities	
	Boy	
	Girl	
	Other gender identities for children	
<p>G: Gender modality</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ One’s experience of gender (i.e., congruence or non-congruence) in relation to the sex assigned at birth⁵⁹. ▪ Cisgender, cis, transgender and trans are adjectives. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • They are used alongside a noun (e.g., cisgender man, cis man, transgender man, trans man). • They are not used with a hyphen (e.g., trans-woman, cis-woman) or making the adjective and noun into one word (e.g., transwoman, ciswoman): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The hyphenated and one-word versions of non-cisgender identities are considered derogatory: underline how cisgender men and women have different gender identity than transgender men and women. ▪ The concept of gender modality helps us understand that trans people have the same gender identities as cis people and rather puts the focus on how both had different journeys in constructing their gender identities. ▪ Gender-diverse people of other gender modalities may or may not also identify as transgender. ▪ Gender-diverse or gender-expansive is an adjective and umbrella term for people who expand notions of gender expression and identity beyond societal gender norms. They may identify as a mix of genders, more binarily as a man or a woman, as agender or genderless. These terms also apply to conceptions of gender outside of the colonial and Western influences. ▪ Gender modality includes, but is not restricted to, the below modalities. 		
	Cisgender (or cis)	<p>• Adjective for people whose gender identity (man or woman) corresponds with their sex assigned at birth.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The term cisgender is beneficial to inclusion in that it acknowledges that there is a unique journey involved in the construction of everyone’s identities, and not that of only trans people. In turn, it contributes to not othering trans, non-binary, and gender-diverse people.
	Cis man	Someone who was assigned male at birth and identifies and lives as a man ⁷
	Cis woman	Someone who was assigned female at birth and identifies and lives as a woman ⁷
	Transgender (or trans)	<p>• Adjective and umbrella term for people whose gender identity (man, woman, non-binary and other gender identities) differs from their sex assigned at birth.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Transgender people experience significant, and well documented multi-level stigma and discrimination (including violence) which impact physical and mental health opportunities and outcomes ^{8, 60}.

		▪ Nonbinary people may or may not consider themselves to be trans ⁷ .
	Trans man	A man who was assigned female at birth but identifies as a man
	Trans woman	A woman who was assigned male at birth but identifies as a woman

G: Gender identity

- A person's internal sense of their own gender⁷.
- Gender identity may or may not correspond to sex assigned at birth.
- We define several other gender identities used in English-speaking Western countries today.
- Avoid using 'non-binary' as a catch all category if possible, as some experience this practice as harmful⁵⁸.

	Man	
	Woman	
	Non-binary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ An umbrella term used to describe gender identities where the individual does not identify exclusively as a man or a woman⁷. ▪ Non-binary people may identify as both a man and woman, partially somewhere in between, neither and other various ways. ▪ There are many categories included within this, such as agender, genderqueer, and genderfluid. ▪ Some nonbinary people may identify as trans, others may not. ▪ Sometimes used as a stand alone gender identify⁶
	Agender	• Adjective for people who do not identify with any gender
	Bigender	• Adjective for people whose gender identity encompasses two genders or is fluid, but within two genders
	Genderqueer	• Adjective for people who reject the boundaries of the gender binary. Some also reject the idea of static gender
	Genderfluid	• Adjective for people who do not adhere to a static gender, and who may move between genders or experience gender as changing, dynamic or evolving
	Boy	
	Girl	
	Demiboy	• Adjective for people who identify partially as men, regardless of sex assigned at birth
	Demigirl	• Adjective for people who identify partially as women, regardless of sex assigned at birth
	Other gender identity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ An umbrella category used to describe people who choose 'other' as the category for their gender identity⁷. ▪ In this category, participants reported, for instance, identifying as agender, genderfluid, gender questioning, genderqueer, or as not identifying with any gender⁷.
	Gender minority	People with a minority gender identity such as trans or nonbinary people ⁷ .

G: Gender expression

- The components of gender that correspond to a person's gendered image (e.g., roles, behaviours, activities, feelings, attitudes, attributes) that communicates aspects of gender to society and influences how individuals are perceived and treated.
- Gender expression may be communicated through someone's names, pronouns, or specific gendered language.
- Although they are often seen as correlated, gender expression is essentially distinct from gender identity.
- Cis, trans, non-binary and gender-diverse people as well as people from any sexual or romantic orientations may be non-conforming in their gender expression regardless of their gender identity.
- Gender expression is always part of a social context and is not static, but rather can change in different contexts and as a function of gender role profiles.

S: Sexual orientation

- How someone identifies in terms of their sexual orientation.
- Describes who a person is emotionally, romantically, or sexually attracted to⁷.
- **Sexual minorities** include persons whose sexual orientation does not conform to the heteronormative standard of heterosexuality, that is, people with a minority sexual orientation such as homosexual (gay, lesbian), bisexual, or pansexual people⁷.
- How sexual identity is summarised and presented will vary from jurisdiction to jurisdiction.
- Language around lesbian, gay, bisexual, trans and intersex (LGBTI+) is evolving.

	Asexual	A person who experiences limited to no sexual attraction ⁷
	Bisexual	A person who is emotionally, romantically, and/or sexually attracted to more than one gender ⁷
	Gay man	A man who is emotionally, romantically, and/or sexually attracted to other men ⁷
	Heterosexual	A person who has an exclusively emotional, romantic and/or sexual orientation towards someone of a different gender ⁷
	Homosexual	A person who is emotionally, romantically, and/or sexually attracted to members of the same gender ⁷
	Lesbian woman	A woman who is emotionally, romantically, and/or sexually attracted to other women ⁷
	Pansexual	A person who is emotionally, romantically, and/or sexually attracted to people regardless of gender ⁷
	Other sexual orientation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ An umbrella category used to describe people who choose 'other' as the category for their sexual orientation⁷. ▪ In this category, participants mentioned, for instance, identifying as demisexual, fluid, polysexual, heteroflexible, homoflexible, queer, questioning, as well as not liking categories⁷
	Minority sexual orientation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Used in this report to refer to anyone not identifying as heterosexual. ▪ This includes people identifying as gay, lesbian, bisexual, pansexual, queer, etc.⁷

Other concepts

	Endosex	A term used to describe persons whose sex characteristics fit normative medical and social ideas for female or male bodies ⁷
	Coming out (public)	When a person first tells someone about their sexual orientation, gender identity, or intersex status ⁷
	Cis-heterosexual	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Cisgender endosex heterosexual ▪ A person whose gender identity matches their sex assigned at birth (i.e., who are not members of gender minorities), who are exclusively attracted to another gender, and who are endosex⁷.
	LGBTIQ+	An abbreviation used to refer to all people who identify as lesbian, gay, bisexual, trans, intersex, queer, or as having any other minority sexual orientation or gender identity ⁷
	Queer	A term used mainly by people to describe their minority sexual orientation and/or gender identity ⁷
	Questioning	The process of exploring your own sexual orientation and/or gender identity ⁷ .
	Romantic orientation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Describes who a person is attracted to in a romantic way. It can be distinct from a person's sexual attraction. ▪ For example, a person could be romantically attracted to a man but have no sexual attraction to him⁷.
	Same-sex marriage	A term used to describe the legal union between two people of the same gender ⁷ .

Appendix 2. Other factors related with intersectionality

Population	Subcategories	Examples
<p>Intersectionality</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> People do not experience inequities separately, and sex and gender research as a whole must be conducted alongside considerations of the influence and interactions of other biological and sociodemographic factors, such as age, race and ethnicity. Intersectionality frameworks can be integrated to facilitate research that is designed to improve health outcomes more equitably⁶¹. We will consider the Interplay of sex and gender with other factors of the "EQUALSS GUIDE Multiple" framework. This framework adds context-specific groups and multiple intersecting disadvantages that are often missed by PROGRESS-Plus⁶². An example is the unique health needs of older LGBTQ+ individuals or disabled people living in underserved areas⁸. 		
<p>E: Ethnicity and Race</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The two concepts are often used interchangeably but they have different histories, and they often associate with migration experiences^{8, 63}. Researchers should be reflective on the way that the use of ethnicity may conflate the impacts of structural racism and/or migration histories depending on their context^{8, 64}. For example, in the UK, racism affects Black people's mental health. However, differences exist both between Black Caribbean and Black African groups and between people born in the country and those who immigrated at some point in their life⁶⁴. Use and acceptance of the terms race, ethnicity and ancestry varies around the world 		
	Ethnicity	A shared cultural background which may include nationality, language, religion, and sometimes common biological characteristics ^{10, 65}
	Race	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A social construct carrying historical divisions made purely on the basis of physical characteristics^{10, 65} Do not use 'Caucasian' as the term is outdated and is associated with racist and pseudoscientific theories about race¹⁰
	Ancestry	Ancestry refers to lineage and can refer to common geographic origin, genealogic, or genetic characteristics ^{10, 65}
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The socioeconomic status (SES) is complex and includes different factors. SES should be considered as a composite measure of related but distinct factors⁸. Different components of the EQUALSS GUIDE Multiple framework reflect SES: Q (Qualifications & Education), I (income and Health), E (Employment & Occupation), U (Underserved area). 		
<p>Q: Qualifications and Education</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Component of SES that captures the human capital (education, knowledge and skills). It is measured at the individual level It links closely with lifestyle choices, social networks, and opportunities in the labour market^{8, 66}. How education levels are summarised and presented will vary from jurisdiction to jurisdiction¹⁰ so we will extract the data as reported in the evidence synthesis. 		
	Add	
	Add	
<p>I: Income and wealth</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Component of SES that captures material resources which can be measured at either the individual or household level and have a strong association with health outcomes^{8, 66}. 		
	Income	
	Wealth	

E: Employment and occupation		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Component of SES that captures both material resources, exposures to health risk factors and aspects of social status within society which have been consistently associated with health outcomes and health inequalities⁸ 		
	Employment	
	Occupation	
U: Underserved area		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Component of SES that captures neighbourhood or area levels of socio-economic deprivation as well as access to services (including health care), green and recreational spaces, exposure to pollution, and transportation connections. Individual and area-based SES measures have independent effects, and hence area-based measures such as Index of Multiple Deprivation (IMD) are included under Underserved area (“U”)⁸ Given that area-based inequality is driven not only by the SES of neighbourhoods, cities, or regions, but also by their geography, urbanity and architecture, and the extent to which they are connected with other areas, Underserved area (“U”) aims to remind researchers to account for the impact of these factors on people’s health⁸ 		
	SES of neighbourhoods, cities, or regions	
	Geography	
	Urbanity	
	Architecture	
A: Age		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Refers to inequalities across age groups, such as working age people and older people. 		
	Add	
L: Language & Religion		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> They can capture the cultural influences on people’s health⁸ Adding language as a distinct dimension invites to pay attention to differences among people in terms of their knowledge and skills in written, spoken and non-spoken language 		
	Language	
	Religion	
D: Disability (physical, mental and learning disabilities)		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Captures physical, mental and learning disabilities, which according to the social model of disability is an important social stratification mechanism⁶⁷ as people are disabled by societal barriers rather than their impairment or difference⁸. Disability has been also found to have directly measurable impacts on health care inequalities, for example through ‘diagnostic overshadowing’ bias^{8,68} and disbelief towards people with disabilities^{8,69}. 		
	Physical disabilities	
	Mental	

	disabilities	
	Learning disabilities	
U: Underrepresented groups		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Captures people who experience severe disadvantage and are excluded both from health care systems and research. The characteristics of such groups differ across contexts ▪ Examples of underrepresented groups are listed below 		
	Vulnerable refugees and asylum seekers	
	People with lived experience of homelessness	
	Substance misuse	
	Criminal justice system	
	Sex workers	
M: Multiple disadvantage		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Captures people who experience disadvantage across multiple dimensions. ▪ Multiple disadvantage is often associated with the experience of underrepresented groups like those described above. ▪ Studying, documenting, and explaining inequality requires the adoption of an intersectional lens. ▪ ‘Multiple’ is meant to be an explicit reminder of this reality and an encouragement for researchers to adopt an intersectional lens⁷⁰. 		
	Example	▪ A South Asian trans man with learning disabilities experiences disadvantage across ethnicity, gender identification and disability
	Example	▪ Rough sleepers often have experience of the justice system, substance misuse and mental health stigma

Appendix 3. Phases in sex- and gender-specific health research

Phase 1. Exploration of sex and gender differences		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Phase 1 identifies areas where sex/gender differences do or do not exist, or quantifies sex/gender differences and similarities in health. This "discovery" phase is a necessary first step in the research cycle. 		
Categories	Subcategories	Examples
1.1. Disease frequency		
	Incidence of a condition	Is Type 2 diabetes incidence higher in men or women?
	Prevalence of a condition	Is Type 2 diabetes prevalence higher in men or women?
1.2. Etiology or risk factors		
Causes or risk /protective factors for a condition		
		Are women are less likely than men to achieve risk factor control leading to worse outcomes?
1.3. Biological mechanisms and pathophysiology		
	Pharmacokinetics	
	Hormones	Is the level of estrogens higher in men or women?
	Genetics	
	Pathophysiology	
1.4. Clinical presentation		
		Do MS symptoms differ by gender?
1.5. Diagnosis test accuracy		
How well a diagnostic test works in terms of its sensitivity and specificity for a particular diagnosis		
	Biological differences in test performance	A diagnostic marker (like troponin in heart attacks) has different baseline levels in males and females, potentially leading to under-diagnosis in women if a single "male-normed" threshold is used
1.6. Prognosis		
The likely course and outcome of a disease, injury, or health condition		
	Overall disease progression	Sex as a prognostic factor for mortality in critically ill adults with sepsis
	Functional outcomes	
	Mental health impact	
1.7. Intervention effects		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Outcomes or changes—both intended (efficacy/effectiveness) or unintended (harms)—that result from implementing an activity, policy, programme, or treatment designed to improve health Sex or gender as a predictors of treatment effects 		
	Preventive intervention	Intervention to reduce the risk of developing a condition <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Infection control Vaccination Healthy diet

		▪ Do statins cause more side effects in women?
	Screening intervention	Early detection to improve outcomes
	Treatment and rehabilitation	
	Policy or programme	
1.8. Health care values and preferences		
	Compliance (treatment adherence)	Is compliance (treatment adherence) with treatment lower in women?
	Acceptability of an intervention	
	Values/preferences	What matters to patients regarding end-of-life care options differ between men and women?
1.9. Health care services and systems		
▪ Sex/gender differences in use of health services (disease prevention, diagnosis and treatment).		
▪ Sex/gender differences in quality of health services (disease prevention, diagnosis and treatment).		
	Economic evaluation	Costs associated with a particular approach/treatment strategy, particularly in terms of cost effectiveness or benefit
	Burden of illness studies or monetary cost studies	
	Use of health services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Are women less likely to uptake of screening? ▪ Women are less likely than men to be screened regularly ▪ Are women less likely to get diagnostic imaging? ▪ Are marginalized gender groups less likely to attend all the planned consultations?
	Quality of health services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Are women less likely to be treated according to the clinical guidelines? ▪ Are women less likely than men to receive an adequate diagnosis?
	Gender representation in health care institutions	▪ Are men more frequently represented as head of unit in health care teams?
1.10. Research systems or institutions		
	Gender representation in research teams	Are men more frequently represented as primary authors in research articles?
	Gender representation in research studies	Are men patients more frequently represented in trials of antidepressants?
	Gender representation in clinical guideline panels	
	Sex/gender-specific recommendations in guidelines	

Phase 2. Explanation of sex and gender differences		
Phase 2 (explanation) moves from identifying sex and gender differences to explaining them, that is, uncovering their underlying causes. Understanding these reasons is critical to determine what can be done to address them. This phase requires evidence on causal pathways.		
Categories	Subcategories	Examples
2.1. Artefactual explanation		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> An observed difference between groups is not a true biological or causal effect. Instead, it arises from the way the study was designed or how the data were analysed. Artefactual explanations explain patterns that are statistical illusions rather than real differences in biology or causality. 		
	Psychometric properties of a test Different reliability and validity of a particular test or assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interview questions might be routinely interpreted in a different way by women and men. Interviews designed by men might be answered less accurately by women.
	Mathematical artefact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> When evaluating sex differences in the associations of risk factors, it is important to consider both the absolute (risk difference) and relative (risk ratio) scales^{14, 71, 72} Sex differences in the association between a risk factor and the disease outcome can be a mathematical artefact explained by the lower basal risk in women or men: If men and women may have different baseline risks for a disease, using relative risk (RR) can create an illusion of a sex difference that disappears when absolute risk difference is calculated. Example: <p>10-year CVD risk without risk factor:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Women = 1% Men = 3% <p>10-year CVD risk with factor:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Women = 2% Men = 4% <p>Absolute Risk Difference:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Women = 1% Men = 1% <p>RR:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Women = $2/1=2$ Men = $4/3=1.33$. <p>Women appear to have a $2/1.33=1.5$ times higher excess risk compared to men on the relative scale, but the absolute impact of the risk factor is identical.</p>
2.2. Biological explanation		
	Sex hormones: Sex differences in health and disease may be explained by differences in sex hormones	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Effects of different oestrogen levels between males and females on health outcomes. Effects of different testosterone levels between males and females on health outcomes. Is hormonal status a mediator of risk?
	Genetics	<p>Genome-wide association study (GWAS)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research approach used to identify genetic variants (usually single nucleotide polymorphisms, SNPs) that are associated with a specific outcome or disease.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Several GWAS have shown that genetic associations of measures of adiposity strongly differ between the sexes. This means that some genes influence adiposity differently in women and men, rather than exerting uniform effects across sexes. See explanation below. ▪ GWAS shows association, not causation, and often points to regions near causal variants rather than the variants themselves.
		<p>Mendelian randomization (MR)</p> <p>MR acts as a "natural experiment," using genetic variants to mimic random allocation. For example, MR can determine if a higher body mass index (BMI) has a different causal impact on heart disease in women versus men, helping to rule out confounding by lifestyle factors.</p> <p>MR helps distinguish whether observed sex differences in risk factor–disease associations reflect real causal differences or are due to confounding, bias, or artefact.⁷³ See example below</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ To test if Body Mass Index (BMI) has different causal effects on coronary heart disease (CHD) in women and men. ▪ Conventional observational studies might show stronger associations in women. But this could be artefactual (e.g., due to different baseline risks, confounding by lifestyle). ▪ MR uses genetic variants linked to BMI as instruments. These variants are randomly allocated and unaffected by lifestyle, so they mimic a natural experiment. ▪ If MR shows that genetically predicted higher BMI increases CHD risk more strongly in women than in men, this supports a true biological sex difference. ▪ If MR shows similar effects, it suggests that differences in observational studies were artefactual or due to confounding.
	Pharmacokinetics	
	<p>Epigenetics</p> <p>It represents a bridge between sex and gender.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Research suggests that social experiences (gender roles) can be "biologically embedded," changing gene expression. ▪ This research explains how gendered social environments translate into biological sex differences.
	Neuroplasticity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Research suggests that social experiences (gender roles) can be "biologically embedded," changing brain structure. ▪ This research that explains how gendered social environments translate into biological sex differences.
	Other biological mechanisms	
2.3. Health care services and systems		
	<p>Health care accessibility</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Sex/gender differences in access to health services (disease prevention, diagnosis and treatment) might explain differences in use of health care services and, thus, the sex differences in disease risk and outcomes. ▪ The Candidacy Framework ⁷⁴ provides a lens for classifying interactions with the health care. This framework considers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Permeability of services (organizational): How easy is it to access the services I need?: The ease at which individuals can gain access to health services, placing particular emphasis on organisational issues related to those services.

	that achieving access to health care is a fluid process that entails different phases.	
	<p>Adjudication (provider bias) The decisions and judgements made by health professionals that act as either barriers or facilitators for the individuals' subsequent access to interventions.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Women's symptoms are frequently dismissed compared to men's in cardiology

Phase 3. Translation to policy and practice

▪ To translate the evidence obtained about sex and gender differences into policy and practice. Once those changes have been made, the actual uptake of policy and practice recommendations also needs to be evaluated. This is where implementation science plays a critical role. The field of implementation science seeks to systematically close the gap between what we know and what we do (often referred to as the know-do gap) by identifying and addressing the barriers that slow or halt the uptake of proven health interventions and evidence-based practices. Evidence for the efficacy (and potential disadvantages) of implementation is required.

Categories	Subcategories	Examples
3.1. Education: Evaluation of interventions to ensure the wide adoption of sex and gender in education of health professionals.		
	Sex/Gender inclusive university curricula	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Training for awareness of unconscious sex bias
	Sex/Gender inclusive post-graduate health professionals training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Procedures to improve sex-specific diagnoses of stroke by ambulance crews. Interventions to reduce sex/gender bias in clinical decision making
3.2. Informed decision-making: Evaluation of interventions for an inclusive informed decision-making, such as clinical guidelines		
	Sex-specific laboratory reference values	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Development of sex-specific laboratory reference values
	Sex/gender-based diagnostic tools	
	Sex/gender-based clinical recommendations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Development of sex-related diagnostic recommendations Interventions to ensure the involvement in a clinical guideline of an individual who is tasked to appraise the literature for evidence on relevant sex differences
3.3. Institutional research system		
<p>▪ Evaluation of interventions tackling systemic factors underpinning sex and gender-disaggregated research and its uptake</p> <p>▪ To reap the benefits of sex and gender analysis, the pillars of science infrastructure must develop and implement coordinated policies⁷⁵.</p>		
	Research teams (such as universities)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Incorporate sex, gender, and intersectional analysis as conceptual tools in technical course in the natural science, medicine, and engineering Increase the diversity of research teams Increase the representation of women in clinical research
	Research publishing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Academic journals mandating that sex and gender are taken into consideration in research
	Research funding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mandatory reporting of sex and gender integration on applicant forms, development of resources for applicants and evaluators, and grant review requirements.

Appendix 4. Eligible evidence syntheses and subtypes

Evidence syntheses	Aim	Examples
1. Systematic reviews		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Systematic reviews (SRs) include quantitative, primary research studies, and aim to summarise, where reasonable, effect estimates across all eligible studies²⁰. MA is a statistical method of synthesising results to calculate one pooled effect across studies⁷⁶. SRs may have meta-analysis (MA) or network meta-analysis (NMA). A MA is optional in a SR, as it is not always possible to conduct (e.g., due to high heterogeneity, lack of comparable studies). A NMA is a MA that combines direct and indirect estimates across a network of interventions in a single analysis. Synonyms are “mixed treatment comparisons” and “multiple treatments meta-analysis”⁷⁷. SRs can answer different questions (see below). 		
1.1. SR of aetiology or risk	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To determine the association between particular exposures/risk factors (e.g., genetic or environmental) and outcomes (e.g., the development of a disease, condition or other health outcome)^{78, 79}. 	Are adults exposed to radon at risk for developing lung cancer? ⁸⁰
1.2. SR of diagnostic test accuracy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To determine how well a test or instrument works (e.g., sensitivity, specificity, likelihood ratio) for a particular diagnosis^{79, 81}. 	What is the diagnostic test accuracy of nutritional tools (such as the Malnutrition Screening Tool) compared to the Patient Generated Subjective Global Assessment amongst patients with colorectal cancer to identify undernutrition? ⁸²
1.3. SR of prevalence or incidence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To determine the prevalence or incidence of a certain condition⁷⁹, that is, to assess how common a condition, symptom, exposure, or characteristic is in a defined population (i.e., the proportion with the outcome at a given time point or period), rather than the effect of an intervention. Prevalence refers to the proportion of a population who have a certain characteristic⁷⁹. Incidence relates to how often the characteristic occurs⁷⁹. 	What is the prevalence/incidence of claustrophobia and claustrophobic reactions in adult patients undergoing MRI? ⁸³
1.4. SR of prognosis^{84, 85}		
1.4.1. Overall prognosis research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To determine the average risk of an outcome (e.g. death) or expected value of an outcome (e.g. pain score) among people with the health condition of interest in a particular 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Survival of women diagnosed with breast cancer in a particular population, time and health care context: In the context of current care, what proportion of women with this condition are expected to be alive at 5 years after diagnosis?

	health care setting.	
1.4.2. Prognostic factor research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify factors whose values (levels) are associated with changes in the outcome risk or expected value. It helps refine prognosis to subgroups of individuals that share the same characteristics, and factors may even identify potential targets for intervention to improve survival. Prognostic factors are also important for the design and analysis of RCTs of interventions, and as adjustment for confounding in observational studies examining treatment effects. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> It focuses on whether particular characteristics of the cancer, the women, their treatment and the health care system, are associated with changes in individual outcome risk (e.g. 5-year survival). To examine whether a novel prognostic factor (e.g. biomarker) adds prognostic value over and above standard prognostic variables (e.g. age, stage of disease). In adults with low back pain, what is the association between individual recovery expectations and disability outcomes?⁸⁶
1.4.3. Prognostic model research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop, validate or assess the impact of a prognostic model to predict an individual's outcome risk or expected outcome value using combinations of prognostic factors. It involves the development, validation and impact assessment of models that use multiple prognostic factors in combination to tailor outcome prediction to individuals. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Such models can be used in everyday practice to help shared decision-making about care - for example, the PREDICT model uses nine factors (age; diagnosis; tumour size, spread, and severity; three biomarkers; therapy) to calculate an individual's 5-year post-surgery survival probability.
1.4.4. Predictors of treatment effect	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify whether subgroups based on individual characteristics (e.g., age, blood pressure, biomarker values) can predict who will and will not benefit from a particular treatment. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Oestrogen receptor status predicted response to treatment with tamoxifen in women with breast cancer, a finding used to target therapy at women who will benefit.
1.5. SR of interventions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Also called effectiveness SRs. Determine the benefits and harms of interventions Effectiveness SRs are by far the most common⁷⁹ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> What is the effectiveness of exercise for treating depression in adults compared to no treatment or a comparison treatment?⁸⁷
1.6. SR of burden of illness studies or monetary cost studies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To synthesise data from burden of illness studies or monetary cost studies. Given the disparity in methods used across such studies, the challenge lies in synthesising the data into a coherent whole.⁷⁸ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> What is the economic burden associated with stroke in adults, compared across countries and income settings, based on cost of illness studies?⁸⁸

1.7. SR of economic evaluation studies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To determine the costs associated with a particular approach/treatment strategy, particularly in terms of cost effectiveness or benefit^{79,89} 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> What is the cost effectiveness of self-monitoring of blood glucose in type 2 diabetes mellitus in high income countries?⁹⁰
1.8. Expert opinion and policy analysis SR*	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To synthesise current expert opinion, text or policy on a certain phenomenon⁷⁹. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> What are the policy strategies to reduce maternal mortality in pregnant and birthing women in Cambodia, Thailand, Malaysia and Sri Lanka?⁹¹
1.9. Psychometric SRs*	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Also called SRs of measurement properties. To evaluate the psychometric properties of a certain test⁷⁹ Allows determining the best tool for use (in terms of its validity, reliability, responsiveness etc.) in practice for a certain condition or factor⁷⁹. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> What is the reliability, validity, responsiveness and interpretability of methods (manual muscle testing, isokinetic dynamometry, hand held dynamometry) to assess muscle strength in adults?⁹²
1.10. Methodology SRs*	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To examine and investigate current research methods and potentially their impact on research quality⁷⁹. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> What is the effect of blind peer review for quantitative studies in terms of the study quality as reported in published reports?⁹³
2. Qualitative reviews		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Also called experiential reviews⁷⁹, their aim is to investigate the experience or meaningfulness of a particular phenomenon⁷⁹. They focus on analysing human experiences and cultural and social phenomena⁷⁹. Qualitative reviews include qualitative studies instead of quantitative studies. Although qualitative reviews typically follow standard evidence synthesis steps, they differ in the frameworks used for formulating questions, the sources searched, and the methods used for study selection and synthesis⁹⁴. Processes of study identification, synthesis, and analysis may be iterative rather than sequential⁹⁴. See more examples in Right Review⁹⁵ 		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Review to explore barriers and facilitators to trial participation⁹⁶. What is the experience of undergoing high technology medical imaging (such as Magnetic Resonance Imaging) in adult patients in high income countries?⁹⁷
3. Mixed methods reviews		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Aim to answer questions regarding effectiveness and safety and contextual factors such as patient experiences or success factors for implementation to provide evidence that extends beyond what works to include questions regarding how, why, and when something may or may not work^{20,98}. Mixed methods reviews synthesise evidence from quantitative and qualitative primary studies to provide a more complete foundation for complex decision-making. They either combine qualitative and quantitative data to answer a review question or analyse these data types separately before integrating the findings⁹⁸. 		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Review with two primary objectives: a) To identify the intervention features that are aligned with successful intervention implementation; b) To assess effectiveness of school-based interventions provided to improve asthma self-management among children⁹⁹
4. Overviews of reviews		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Overviews of reviews aim to provide a broad, comprehensive overview of existing evidence syntheses. Overviews of reviews are evidence syntheses that include (usually systematic) reviews or qualitative evidence syntheses instead of primary studies¹⁰⁰. They may report outcome data exactly as presented in the included SRs or they re-analyse the data, for example, by calculating their own meta-analyses¹⁰⁰. They are especially useful in areas where multiple up-to-date SRs exist. They should not be done on topics where many relevant studies are not yet included in SRs. 		
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Summarizing the current epidemiological evidence from SRs and MA linking ambient air pollution and CVDs, with a focus on

		geographical differences and vulnerable subpopulations ¹⁰¹
5. Big picture reviews		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ An overarching term for scoping reviews, mapping reviews, and evidence gap maps. ▪ These subtypes follow the stages of the review process but do not synthesise evidence or produce common effect measures. ▪ They aim to describe, organise, and map the evidence, providing an overview of the existing research. ▪ Big picture reviews help decision-makers- take stock of what types of evidence exist, how key concepts are defined in the literature, and where research is concentrated or lacking in a specific field¹⁰². 		
5.1. Scoping reviews	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ ES that aims “to systematically identify and map the breadth of evidence available on a particular topic, field, concept, or issue, often irrespective of source (i.e., primary research, reviews, and nonempirical evidence) within or across particular contexts. Scoping reviews can clarify key concepts/ definitions in the literature and identify key characteristics or factors related to a concept, including those related to methodological research”⁷⁴. ▪ A key distinction is also that scoping reviews can be either deductive or inductive in approach, while mapping reviews or evidence gap maps are typically deductive, following predefined frameworks or categories 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Investigate the prevalence of PD in regional, rural and remote areas of Australia, to inform the provision of equitable PD-specific care¹⁰³
5.2. Mapping reviews and “Evidence and Gap Maps”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ ES that aims to catalogue the available evidence on a question of interest¹⁰⁴. ▪ The identified evidence can be presented graphically, often in the form of an evidence gap map that displays the available evidence, web-based, and interactively with the option of filtering and linking to the underlying references¹⁰⁵. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Explore what types of studies (RCTs, cohort studies, etc.) are available on specific comparisons and outcomes¹⁰⁶
<p>Abbreviations: ES: evidence synthesis. SR: systematic review.</p> <p>* Evidence synthesis types marked with asterisk were taken from the cited source. If otherwise not stated, the categories were taken from Nussbaumer-Streit et al²⁰. Some examples are taken from Munn et al⁷⁹</p>		

Appendix 5. Search strategy and filters

I. Evidence syntheses			
1	Systematic and non-systematic reviews	(("meta-analysis as topic"[MeSH] OR "Network Meta-Analysis"[Mesh] OR "systematic reviews as topic"[MeSH] OR "review literature as topic"[MeSH] OR "review"[pt] OR "systematic review"[pt] OR "meta-analysis"[pt] OR "Historical Article"[pt] OR "review*"[Title/Abstract] OR "systematic map"[Title/Abstract] OR "overview"[Title/Abstract] OR "Systematic search*"[Title/Abstract] OR "meta-analy*"[Title/Abstract] OR "Bibliographies as Topic"[MeSH]) NOT (comment[pt] OR letter[pt] OR "Editorial"[pt])	High-sensitivity filter validated by Fontanive et al 2025 ¹⁰⁷
2	Bibliometric analyses	(bibliometrics[MeSH:noexp] OR bibliometric[TIAB] OR bibliometry[TIAB] OR "citation analyses"[TIAB::~2] OR "citation analysis"[TIAB::~2] OR informetrics[TIAB] OR "statistical semantics"[TIAB::~2])	Source: Health Sciences Library System, University of Pittsburgh https://hsls.libguides.com/PubMed-search-filters Updated June 11 2025 Bibliometric analyses are often included as "systematic reviews" in indexing. However, they are closer to scoping reviews or mapping reviews in that they seek to enumerate or map studies by topic, location, or other variables. The term has not been included in the Sutton et al article, but a search filter for them is below traditional literature reviews.
3		#1 OR #2	
II. Sex and Gender			
4	Identifying sex- and gender-specific health literature	(sex based OR sex factors OR sex distribution OR sex characteristics OR sex dimorphism OR gender difference* OR female) AND (gender[ti] OR sex[ti] OR women[ti] OR female[ti])	PubMed search tool: Expanded Texas Tech University Health Sciences Center sex- and gender-specific health ¹⁰⁸
III. Sexual minorities			
5	Sexual minorities	(bisexuality[MeSH:noexp] OR "Disorders of Sex Development"[MeSH:noexp] OR "gender identity"[MeSH:noexp] OR "Health Services for Transgender Persons"[MeSH:noexp] OR homosexuality[MeSH:noexp] OR homosexuality, female[MeSH:noexp] OR homosexuality, male[MeSH:noexp] OR "Intersex Persons"[MeSH:noexp] OR "sex reassignment	Updated April 10, 2025 Sexual minorities (VERY broad based partially on the PubMed filter)

		<p>procedures"[MeSH:noexp] OR "sex reassignment surgery"[MeSH:noexp] OR "Sexual and Gender Disorders"[MeSH:noexp] OR "Sexual and Gender Minorities"[MeSH:noexp] OR "Transgender Persons"[MeSH:noexp] OR transsexualism[MeSH:noexp] OR bigender[TIAB] OR bisexual[TIAB] OR bisexuality[TIAB] OR bisexuals[TIAB] OR ("disorders sex"[TIAB::~1] OR "disorders sexual"[TIAB::~1]) AND ("sex development"[TIAB::~1] OR "sexual development"[TIAB::~1])) OR homosexuality[TIAB] OR gay[TIAB] OR gays[TIAB] OR "gender change"[TIAB::~1] OR "gender confirmation"[TIAB::~1] OR "gender disorder"[TIAB::~1] OR "gender diverse"[TIAB::~1] OR "gender diversities"[TIAB::~1] OR "gender diversity"[TIAB::~1] OR "gender dysphoria"[TIAB::~1] OR "gender identity"[TIAB::~1] OR "gender minorities"[TIAB::~1] OR "gender minority"[TIAB::~1] OR ("gender non"[TIAB::~1] AND "non conforming"[TIAB::~1]) OR "gender nonconforming"[TIAB::~1] OR "gender orientation"[TIAB::~1] OR genderqueer[TIAB] OR "gender reassignment"[TIAB::~1] OR "gender surgery"[TIAB::~1] OR GLBT*[TIAB] OR homophile[TIAB] OR homophilia[TIAB] OR homosexual[TIAB] OR homosexuals[TIAB] OR intersex[TIAB] OR lesbian[TIAB] OR lesbianism[TIAB] OR lesbians[TIAB] OR LGBBQT[TIAB] OR LGBT*[TIAB] OR "males who have sex with"[TIAB] OR "men having sex with men"[TIAB] OR "men who had sex with men"[TIAB] OR "men who have had sex with men"[TIAB] OR "men who have sex with both men"[TIAB] OR "men who have sex with men"[TIAB] OR "men who have sex with other men"[TIAB] OR nonheterosexual[TIAB] OR "non heterosexual"[TIAB::~1] OR "non heterosexuality"[TIAB::~1] OR "non heterosexuals"[TIAB::~1] OR nonheterosexual*[TIAB] OR "non binary"[TIAB::~1] OR nonbinary[TIAB] OR pansexual[TIAB] OR polysexual[TIAB] OR queer[TIAB] OR "same sex"[TIAB::~1] OR "sex change"[TIAB::~1] OR "sex reassignment"[TIAB::~1] OR "sexual diversity"[TIAB::~1] OR "sexual minorities"[TIAB::~1] OR "sexual minority"[TIAB::~1] OR "sexual orientation"[TIAB::~1] OR "sexual reassignment"[TIAB::~1] OR transgender[TIAB] OR transgendered[TIAB] OR transgenderism[TIAB] OR transgenders[TIAB] OR transman[TIAB] OR "trans men"[TIAB::~1] OR transmen[TIAB] OR transsexual[TIAB] OR transsexualism[TIAB] OR transsexuals[TIAB] OR transwoman[TIAB] OR "trans women"[TIAB::~1] OR transwomen[TIAB] OR "two spirit"[TIAB::~1] OR "women who have sex with women"[TIAB])</p>	<p>Developed by Helena VonVille</p>
6	<p>Child and adolescent sexual minorities</p>	<p>((("Adolescent"[MeSH:noexp] OR "Adolescent Development"[MeSH:noexp] OR "Child"[MeSH:noexp] OR "Child Development"[MeSH:noexp] OR Schools[MeSH:noexp] OR adolescence[TIAB] OR adolescent[TIAB] OR adolescents[TIAB] OR child[TIAB] OR children[TIAB] OR teen[TIAB] OR teenager[TIAB] OR teenagers[TIAB] OR youth[TIAB]) AND (bisexuality[MeSH:noexp] OR gender identity[MeSH:noexp] OR homosexuality[MeSH:noexp] OR homosexuality, female[MeSH:noexp] OR homosexuality, male[MeSH:noexp] OR "Sexual and Gender Minorities"[MeSH:noexp] OR sex reassignment procedures[MeSH:noexp] OR sex reassignment surgery[MeSH:noexp] OR "Transgender Persons"[MeSH:noexp] OR transsexualism[MeSH:noexp] OR bisexual[TIAB] OR bisexuals[TIAB] OR gay[TIAB] OR gays[TIAB] OR gender change[TIAB] OR gender confirmation[TIAB] OR "gender diverse"[TIAB::~1] OR "gender diversities"[TIAB::~1] OR "gender diversity"[TIAB::~1] OR "gender identity"[TIAB::~1] OR "gender minorities"[TIAB::~1] OR "gender minority"[TIAB::~1] OR "gender queer"[TIAB::~1] OR genderqueer[TIAB] OR GLBT*[TIAB] OR homosexual[TIAB] OR homosexuality[TIAB] OR homosexuals[TIAB] OR LGBT*[TIAB] OR lesbian[TIAB] OR lesbianism[TIAB] OR lesbians[TIAB] OR</p>	<p>Updated 3 September 2024 Developed by Helena VonVille</p>

		"male homosexuality"[TIAB:~1] OR ("men having"[TIAB:~1] AND "sex men"[TIAB:~1]) OR ("men who"[TIAB:~1] AND "sex men"[TIAB:~1]) OR ("men who"[TIAB:~1] AND "other men"[TIAB:~1]) OR MSM[TIAB] OR "non heterosexual"[TIAB:~1] OR "non heterosexuals"[TIAB:~1] OR nonheterosexual*[TIAB] OR pansexual[TIAB] OR polysexual[TIAB] OR queer[TIAB] OR "same sex"[TIAB:~1] OR "sex change"[TIAB:~1] OR "sex reassignment"[TIAB:~1] OR "sexual diversity"[TIAB:~1] OR "sexually diverse"[TIAB:~1] OR "sexual minorities"[TIAB:~1] OR "sexual minority"[TIAB:~1] OR "sexual orientation"[TIAB:~1] OR transgender[TIAB] OR transgendered[TIAB] OR transgenderism[TIAB] OR transgenders[TIAB] OR ("women having"[TIAB:~1] AND "sex women"[TIAB:~1]) OR ("women who"[TIAB:~1] AND "sex women"[TIAB:~1]) OR ("women who"[TIAB:~1] AND "other women"[TIAB:~1])) OR "trans adolescent"[TIAB:~1] OR "trans adolescents"[TIAB:~1] OR "trans child"[TIAB:~1] OR "trans children"[TIAB:~1] OR "trans student"[TIAB:~1] OR "trans students"[TIAB:~1] OR "trans youth"[TIAB:~1])	
7	Non-gender conforming	(gender identity[MeSH:noexp] OR bigender[TIAB] OR "gender diverse"[TIAB:~1] OR "gender diversities"[TIAB:~1] OR "gender diversity"[TIAB:~1] OR "gender identity"[TIAB:~1] OR "gender dysphoria"[TIAB:~1] OR "gender minorities"[TIAB:~1] OR ("gender non"[TIAB:~1] AND "non conforming"[TIAB:~1]) OR "gender nonconforming"[TIAB:~1] OR "non heterosexual"[TIAB:~1] OR "non heterosexuals"[TIAB:~1] OR nonheterosexual*[TIAB] OR pansexual[TIAB] OR polysexual[TIAB] OR "two spirit"[TIAB:~1])	Updated 6 October 2023 Developed by Helena VonVille
8	Sexual development	("Disorders of Sex Development"[MeSH:noexp] OR "Sexual and Gender Disorders"[MeSH:noexp] OR ("disorders sex"[TIAB:~1] OR "disorders sexual"[TIAB:~1]) AND ("sex development"[TIAB:~1] OR "sexual development"[TIAB:~1])) OR "gender disorder"[TIAB:~1] OR "gender disorders"[TIAB:~1] OR "gender dysphoria"[TIAB:~1] OR "Intersex Persons"[MeSH:noexp] OR (hermaphroditism[TIAB] NOT ((animals[mesh] OR plants[mesh]) NOT humans[mesh])) OR intersex[TIAB] OR intersexuality[TIAB])	Updated 6 October 2023 Developed by Helena VonVille
9		#5 OR #6 OR #7 OR #8	
IV. Transgender people			
10	Transgender people	("Transgender Persons"[MeSH:noexp] OR transsexualism[MeSH:noexp] OR "gender change"[TIAB:~1] OR "gender expansive"[TIAB:~1] OR "gender expansiveness"[TIAB:~1] OR "trans gender"[TIAB:~1] OR "trans genders"[TIAB:~1] OR "trans man"[TIAB:~1] OR "trans men"[TIAB:~1] OR "trans woman"[TIAB:~1] OR "trans women"[TIAB:~1] OR transgender[TIAB] OR transgendered[TIAB] OR transgenderism[TIAB] OR transgenders[TIAB] OR transman[TIAB] OR transmen[TIAB] OR transpeople[TIAB] OR transsexual[TIAB] OR transsexualism[TIAB] OR transsexuality[TIAB] OR transsexualism[TIAB] OR transsexuals[TIAB] OR transwoman[TIAB] OR transwomen[TIAB])	Updated April 10, 2025 Developed by Helena VonVille
11	Transgender people health care terms	(gender-affirming procedures[mesh:noexp] OR puberty suppression[mesh:noexp] OR gender-affirming surgery[mesh:noexp] OR "Health Services for Transgender Persons"[mesh:noexp] OR "sex reassignment procedures"[mesh:noexp] OR "sex reassignment surgery"[mesh:noexp] OR "affirming care"[tiab:~3] OR "affirming dental"[tiab:~3] OR "affirming environment"[tiab:~3] OR "affirming healthcare"[tiab:~3] OR "affirming medical"[tiab:~3] OR "gender affirming"[TIAB:~1] OR "gender confirmation"[TIAB:~1] OR "sex change"[TIAB:~1] OR "sex reassignment"[TIAB:~1])	Updated April 10, 2025 Developed by Helena VonVille
12		#10 OR #11	

V. Gay, lesbian, bisexual, pansexual, polysexual people			
13	People who identify as male	homosexuality, male[MeSH:noexp] OR "homosexual men"[TIAB:~1] OR "male homosexuality"[TIAB:~1] OR ("men having"[TIAB:~1] AND "sex men"[TIAB:~1]) OR ("men who"[TIAB:~1] AND "sex men"[TIAB:~1]) OR ("men who"[TIAB:~1] AND "other men"[TIAB:~1]) OR MSM[TIAB] OR ((men[MeSH:noexp] OR male[TIAB] OR males[TIAB] OR men[TIAB]) AND (bisexuality[MeSH:noexp] OR gender identity[MeSH:noexp] OR homosexuality[MeSH:noexp] OR "Sexual and Gender Minorities"[MeSH:noexp] OR bisexual[TIAB] OR bisexuals[TIAB] OR gay[TIAB] OR gays[TIAB] OR "gender identity"[TIAB:~1] OR "gender minorities"[TIAB:~1] OR "gender minority"[TIAB:~1] OR "gender queer"[TIAB:~1] OR genderqueer[TIAB] OR GLBT*[TIAB] OR homosexual[TIAB] OR homosexuality[TIAB] OR homosexuals[TIAB] OR LGBT*[TIAB] OR nonheterosexual[TIAB] OR "non heterosexual"[TIAB:~1] OR "non heterosexuals"[TIAB:~1] OR nonheterosexual*[TIAB] OR pansexual[TIAB] OR polysexual[TIAB] OR queer[TIAB] OR "same sex"[TIAB:~1] OR "sexual diversity"[TIAB:~1] OR "sexually diverse"[TIAB:~1] OR "sexual minorities"[TIAB:~1] OR "sexual minority"[TIAB:~1] OR "sexual orientation"[TIAB:~1]))	Updated 6 October 2023 Developed by Helena VonVille
14	People who identify as female	(homosexuality, female[MeSH:noexp] OR "female homosexuality"[TIAB:~1] OR "female homosexuals"[TIAB:~1] OR "homosexual females "[TIAB:~1] OR lesbian[TIAB] OR lesbianism[TIAB] OR lesbians[TIAB] OR ("women who"[TIAB:~1] AND "sex women"[TIAB:~1]) OR ("women who"[TIAB:~1] AND "other women"[TIAB:~1]) OR ((women[MeSH:noexp] OR female[TIAB] OR females[TIAB] OR women[TIAB]) AND (bisexuality[MeSH:noexp] OR gender identity[MeSH:noexp] OR homosexuality[MeSH:noexp] OR "Sexual and Gender Minorities"[MeSH:noexp] OR bisexual[TIAB] OR bisexuals[TIAB] OR gay[TIAB] OR gays[TIAB] OR "gender identity"[TIAB:~1] OR "gender minorities"[TIAB:~1] OR "gender minority"[TIAB:~1] OR "gender queer"[TIAB:~1] OR genderqueer[TIAB] OR GLBT*[TIAB] OR homosexual[TIAB] OR homosexuality[TIAB] OR homosexuals[TIAB] OR LGBT*[TIAB] OR nonheterosexual[TIAB] OR "non heterosexual"[TIAB:~1] OR "non heterosexuals"[TIAB:~1] OR nonheterosexual*[TIAB] OR pansexual[TIAB] OR polysexual[TIAB] OR queer[TIAB] OR "same sex"[TIAB:~1] OR "sexual diversity"[TIAB:~1] OR "sexually diverse"[TIAB:~1] OR "sexual minorities"[TIAB:~1] OR "sexual minority"[TIAB:~1] OR "sexual orientation"[TIAB:~1]))	Updated 25 March 2024 Developed by Helena VonVille
15	Bisexuality	"bisexuality"[MeSH] OR bisexual*[tw] OR "homosexually experienced"[tiab: ~ 1] OR lgbt*[tw] OR "men who have sex with men"[tw] OR msmw[tw] OR nonheterosexual*[tw]	Sensitivity-maximizing search filter developed by Morgan-Daniel et al for bisexuality ¹⁰⁹
16		#13 OR #14 OR #15	
VI. Total			
17		#3 AND (#4 OR #9 OR #12 OR #16)	

Appendix 6. Draft data extraction form: sex and gender concepts and terms

We will describe sex and gender considerations in the included studies based on Adisso et al⁴³ framework. These criteria were based on the definitions of sex and gender proposed by the Canadian Institutes of Health Research (CIHR)⁴⁵, and the U.S National Institutes of Health (NIH)⁴⁶. Asterisk (*) mark criteria/examples added by our scoping review team not detailed in the original sources.

1. Sex and gender terms used		
	Sex terms	
	Detail	For example, “males”
	Detail	
	Gender terms	
	Detail	
	Detail	
	Gender identity terms	
	Detail	
	Detail	
	Gender modality terms	
	Detail	
	Detail	
	Gender expression terms	
	Detail	
	Detail	
	Sexual orientation terms	
	Detail	
	Detail	
	Other terms	
	Detail	
2. * Definitions used for sex and gender		
Assessment based on the SAGER (<i>Reporting of Sex and Gender Equity in Research</i>) guidelines definitions ³ .		
	Sex	
	Compatible with SAGER	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ A set of biological attributes in humans and animals that are associated with physical and physiological features including chromosomes, gene expression, hormone function and reproductive/sexual anatomy³.
	Non-compatible with SAGER	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Definitions different to SAGER guidelines.
	Unclear definition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ No sex definition is provided. ▪ However, sex-related categories are detailed.
	No definition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ No sex definition is provided ▪ No sex-related categories are detailed.
	Not applicable	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Authors did not use sex-related terms.
	Gender	
	Compatible with SAGER	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The socially constructed roles, behaviours and identities of female, male and gender diverse people³.
	Non-compatible with SAGER	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Definitions different to SAGER guidelines.
	Unclear definition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ No gender definition is provided ▪ However, gender-related categories are detailed.
	No definition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ No definition for gender is provided ▪ No gender-related categories are detailed.
	Not applicable	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Authors did not use gender-related terms.
3. Non-binary use of sex and gender		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ When authors mention the terms sex or gender, do they describe them by using more than two categories? ▪ Consider a non-binary operationalisation of sex or gender if review authors used the terms sex or gender and applied them considering also at least a third category to consider variations (e.g., intersex, individuals with differences of sex development, gender diverse, not specified, or ‘Would prefer not to respond’). 		

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consider a binary operationalisation of sex or gender, if review authors used the terms sex or gender and applied them by distinguishing two categories, even when these categories were inferred (see examples below). Assess this criterion in studies in which the terms sex and/or gender (i.e. sex, gender or both) were mentioned: if these terms were not used, mark this criterion as 'Not applicable'. 	
Sex	
Non-binary use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Authors mention the term sex and describe it using more than two categories, such as male, female, intersex. Intersex person is a person whose sex characteristics (e.g., chromosomes, gonads, hormones, or external/internal reproductive organs) do not align with typical binary notions of male or female bodies. Examples of options for the third category: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Intersex ✓ Person with differences of sex development (DSD) ✓ 'Not specified' ✓ 'Would prefer not to respond'
Binary use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Authors mention the term sex and describe it using two categories, such as male and female. Examples: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ "All the studies enrolled participants of both sexes" (without using sex-related terms). ✓ "Sex (M/F): intervention 40/30; control group; 50/25 (...) M/F - male/female" Authors mention the term sex and describe it using two gender categories (women and men) Examples: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ "Sex (Women/Men): intervention 40/30; control group; 50/25 (...)" Consider the use of terms as binary if authors mention the term sex and describe it by using only one category (i.e. male or female). Thus, in instances where categories must be inferred, we will assume binary use. Example: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Authors only report the proportion of female participants as 65%. We will infer that the proportion of male participants was 35% and consider that a binary-sex was used.
Unclear non-binary use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Authors mention only the term "sex" without specifying categories.
Not applicable	The review did not use neither sex nor sex-related terms.
Gender	
Non-binary use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Authors mention the term gender and describe it using more than two categories: Woman (she), man (he), other categories (they), such as gender diverse or non-binary. Girl, boy, other categories Examples of options for the third category: non-binary, agender, bigender, genderqueer, genderfluid.
Binary use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Authors mention the term gender and describe it using two categories: woman, man or girl, boy. Examples: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ "All the studies enrolled participants of both genders" (without using sex-related terms). ✓ "Gender (Woman/Man): intervention 40/30; control group; 50/25 (...)" Authors mention the term gender and describe it using two sex categories (male and female)

		<p>Examples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ “Gender (Male/Female): intervention 40/30; control group; 50/25 (...) <p>▪ Consider the use of terms as binary if authors mention the term gender and describe it by using only one category (i.e. woman or man, or girl or boy). Thus, in instances where categories must be inferred, we will assume binary use.</p> <p>Example:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Authors only report the proportion of women as 65%. We will infer that the proportion of men was 35% and consider that a binary-gender was used.
	Unclear non-binary use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Authors mention only the term “gender” without specifying categories.
	Not applicable	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The review did not use neither gender nor gender-related terms.
4. Categories used to describe sex and gender		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ When authors mention the terms sex or gender, do they use consistently the corresponding related-categories, according to the current international definitions? ▪ Assess the use of categories for sex and gender in studies in which sex, gender or both were mentioned. 		
Use of sex categories		
	Appropriate categories for sex	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Authors use consistently sex categories, such as male, female or intersex. ▪ *If authors use consistently male or female categories for sex without mentioning intersex: consider the use of sex categories as appropriate (but judge binary use of sex, see above).
	Inappropriate categories for sex	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Authors mention the term sex but use the categories associated with gender to describe sex. ▪ Example: “We evaluated sex, categorised as men or women”
	Unclear categories for sex	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Authors mention the term sex without subdividing into categories. * Authors mention consistently sex categories (either binary or non-binary), but do not mention the term sex. * Example: “We included 50 female participants and 60 male participants” (without using the term sex in the article)
	Not applicable	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Authors did not use neither sex nor sex-related terms.
Use of gender categories		
	Appropriate categories for gender	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Authors use consistently gender categories such as girl, woman, boy or man or any word applying to gender-diverse people. * If authors use consistently man or woman categories for gender without mentioning gender diverse people: consider the use of gender categories as appropriate (but judge binary use of gender, see above).
	Inappropriate categories for gender	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Authors mention the term gender but use the categories associated with sex to describe gender. ▪ Example: “We evaluated gender, categorised as males and females” ▪ Example: “Gender (male/female): intervention=100:80; control = 120:110”. “Gender identity: not stated”
	Unclear categories for gender	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Authors mention the term gender without subdividing into categories. * Authors mention consistently gender categories (either binary or non-binary), but do not mention the term gender. *Example: “We included 50 women and 60 men” (without

		using the term gender in the article)
	Not applicable	▪ Authors did not use neither gender nor gender-related terms.
5. Non-interchangeable use of sex and gender		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ When authors mention sex, gender, or related terms, do they use them interchangeably? ▪ Assess this criterion in studies in which sex and/or gender and/or related terms were mentioned. 		
	Non-interchangeable use of sex and gender	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Sex- and gender-related terms were used non-interchangeably ▪ Sex terms were consistently used to describe biological attributes while gender terms were consistently used to describe sociocultural attributes of study participants.
	Interchangeable use of sex and gender	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Sex-related terms (sex, female, male, intersex) and gender-related terms (gender, girl, boy, woman, man, gender-diverse) were mentioned and indiscriminately used to describe either sex or gender of participants in the same study. ▪ Examples: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Authors use sex terms while describing the sociodemographic characteristics but report or discuss the results using gender terms to describe the same attributes of the same participants ✓ “Table of included studies: control group: 10 cases (8 males, 2 females) (...) 50 patients (36 men and 14 women)” ✓ “We evaluated sex, categorised as male or female and the sample included 10% of women” ✓ “We evaluated gender, categorised as men, women or gender diverse and the sample included 10% of female participants”
	Unclear non-interchangeable use of sex and gender	▪ Other situations that apply
	Not applicable	▪ Authors did not use neither gender nor gender-related terms.

Appendix 7. Draft data extraction form for scoping review and the Evidence and Gap Map

Codes for the Evidence and Gap Map are shown in green.

I. Sustainable Development Goal-3 (SDG-3)

I. Sustainable Development Goal-3 (SDG-3)	
Ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages ⁴⁴	
Maternal health	
	Abnormal progress of labor
	Anesthetic techniques
	Antenatal care
	Asymptomatic bacteriuria in pregnancy
	Breastfeeding
	Caesarean section
	Diabetes and pregnancy
	Ectopic pregnancy
	Family planning
	Hypertensive disorders of pregnancy
	Induction of labor
	Instrumental delivery
	Labor and delivery
	Labour monitoring
	Large for gestational age
	Long labor
	Maternal infections
	Maternal malnutrition
	Miscarriage, stillbirth and abortion
	Obstetric procedures
	Obstetric thromboembolism
	Obstetric trauma
	Obstetrical bleeding
	Pain during labor
	Perineal trauma
	Postpartum period
	Prelabor rupture of membranes
	Uterine rupture
Infant Health	
	Breastfeeding
	Child abuse
	Childhood diseases
	Children's exposure to substances
	Newborn health
	Pediatric cancer
	Pediatric mental health
	Pediatric neurological conditions
	Pediatric obesity
	Pediatric respiratory diseases
	Perinatal asphyxia
	Preterm/low birth weight
Communicable Diseases	
	Anthrax

Antimicrobial resistance	
Ascariasis	
Brucellosis	
COVID-19	
Chagas disease	
Cholera	
Crimean–Congo hemorrhagic fever	
Dengue	
Epidemic typhus	
Gnathostomiasis	
HIV	
Histoplasmosis	
Infectious diarrhea	
Japanese encephalitis	
Leishmaniasis	
Malaria	
Measles	
Melioidosis	
Meningitis	
Monkeypox	
Neglected tropical diseases	
Paracoccidioidomycosis	
Pediculosis capitis	
Plague	
Pneumonia	
Scabies	
Scrub typhus	
Sepsis	
Sexually transmitted infections	
Smallpox	
Snakebite	
Strongyloidiasis	
Syphilis	
Taenia solium infection	
Trichomoniasis	
Tuberculosis	
Typhoid and paratyphoid	
Viral hepatitis	
Zika virus disease	
Non-Communicable Diseases	
Asthma	
COPD	
Cancer	
Cerebrovascular diseases	
Chronic kidney disease	
Connective tissue diseases	
Dementia	
Dental disorders	
Diabetes	
Ear, nose, and throat disorders	
Endocrine disorders	
Epilepsy	
Eye disorders	
Gastrointestinal disorders	
Headaches	

	Hematological conditions	
	Hypertension	
	Ischemic heart diseases	
	Liver cirrhosis	
	Mental health	
	Migraine	
	Nutrition and metabolic disorders	
	Parkinson disease	
	Salt consumption	
	Sedentary lifestyle	
	Sickle cell disease	
	Thalassemia	
	Trauma, poisoning and injuries	
Consumption of Psychoactive Substances		
	Alcohol	
	Amphetamines	
	Cannabis	
	Cocaine	
	Hallucinogens	
	Inhalants	
	Opioids	
	Sedative hypnotics	
	Substance use disorder	
Sexual and Reproductive Health care		
	Domestic violence	
	Family planning	
	Infertility	
	Miscarriage, stillbirth and abortion	
	Pregnant adolescents	
	Safe abortion services	
	Sexual abuse	
	Sexually transmitted infections	
Universal Health		
	Delivery arrangements	
	Financial arrangements	
	Governance arrangements	
Air, Water and Soil Pollution		
	Accidental poisoning	
	Occupational or environmental exposure	
	Soil pollution	
	WASH interventions	
	Water pollution	
Health Workforce		
	Health associate professionals	
	Health management and support personnel	
	Health professionals	
	Personal care workers in health services	
National and Global Health Risks		
	Earth movement disasters	
	Infectious PH emergencies	
	Man-made disasters	
	Weather-related disasters	
Road Traffic Accidents		
	Cyclists	
	Motor vehicle drivers	

	Pedestrians	
	Road traffic injuries	
Tobacco Control		
	Smoking cessation	
	Tobacco control policies	
Vaccine and Medicine Development		
Pregnant woman		
	Asymptomatic bacteriuria in pregnancy	
	Pregnant adolescents	
Venous thromboembolism		
Multiple sclerosis		
Congenital disorders		
Air quality		
Multiple targets		
Other		
Reporting		
	Reported	
	Reported but unclear	
	Not reported	
Handling by reviewers		
	As reported by the authors	
	Assumed by the reviewers	
	Corrected by the reviewers	

II. Health condition

II. Health condition		
Health conditions as listed in the International Classification of Diseases (ICD) 11th Revision ³⁸ . See examples below		
01. Certain infections or parasitic diseases		
	Gastroenteritis or colitis of Infectious origin	
	Bacterial intestinal infections	
02. Neoplasm		
	Neoplasms of central nervous system or related structures	
	Primary neoplasms of brain	
	
...		
Multi-condition		
Other		
Reporting		
	Reported	
	Reported but unclear	
	Not reported	
Handling of terms by reviewers		
	As reported by the authors	
	Assumed by the reviewers	
	Corrected by the reviewers	

III. Sex/gender population

III. Sex/gender population		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sex/gender population/aspect that the evidence synthesis targets. Mark as many option as applicable. Example: Review focused on intersex participants – Mark Intersex 		
Sex		
	Males & Females & Intersex	
	Males & Females	

	Males	
	Females	
	Intersex	
	Not applicable	
	Handling by reviewers	
	As reported by the authors	
	Assumed by the reviewers	
	Corrected by the reviewers	
Gender identity		
	Men & Women	
	Men	
	Women	
	Other gender identities	
	Non-binary	
	Agender	
	Bigender	
	Genderqueer	
	Genderfluid	
	Add as needed	
	Other-Not specified	
	Boy	
	Girl	
	Other gender identities in children	
	Demiboy	
	Demigirl	
	Add as needed	
	Other-Not specified	
	Handling by reviewers	
	As reported by the authors	
	Assumed by the reviewers	
	Corrected by the reviewers	
Gender modality		
	Cisgender & Transgender	
	Cisgender (or cis)	
	Transgender (or trans)	
	Handling by reviewers	
	As reported by the authors	
	Assumed by the reviewers	
	Corrected by the reviewers	
Sexual orientation		
	Bisexual	
	Gay	
	Heterosexual	
	Lesbian	
	Other sexual identities	
	Handling by reviewers	
	As reported by the authors	
	Assumed by the reviewers	
	Corrected by the reviewers	
Multiple sex groups		
Multiple gender groups		
Other sex groups		
	Detail	
	Detail	
Other gender groups		

Detail	
Detail	

IV. Research phase

IV. Research phase	
Phase 1. Exploration of sex and gender differences	
	Disease frequency
	Etiology or risk factors
	Biological mechanisms and pathophysiology
	Clinical presentation
	Diagnosis test accuracy
	Prognosis
	Health interventions
	Sex or gender as a predictors of treatment effects
	Health care values and preferences
	Compliance (treatment adherence)
	Acceptability of an intervention
	Values/preferences
	Health care services and systems
	Economic evaluation
	Burden of illness studies or monetary cost studies
	Use of health services
	Quality of health services
	Gender representation in health care institutions
	Research systems or institutions
	Gender representation in research teams
	Gender representation in research studies
	Gender representation in clinical guideline panels
	Sex/gender-specific guidelines
	Other
	Unclear
Phase 2. Explanation of sex and gender differences	
	Artefactual explanation
	Psychometric properties of a certain test
	Mathematical artefact
	Biological explanation
	Sex hormones
	Genetics
	Pharmacokinetics
	Epigenetics
	Neuroplasticity
	Other biological mechanisms
	Health care services and systems
	Health care accessibility
	Adjudication (provider bias)
	Other
	Unclear
Phase 3. Translation to policy and practice	
	Education
	Sex/Gender inclusive university curricula
	Sex/Gender inclusive post-graduate health professionals training
	Informed decision-making
	Sex-specific laboratory reference values
	Sex/gender-based diagnostic tools

	Sex/gender-based clinical recommendations	
	Institutional research system	
	Research teams (such as universities)	
	Research publishing	
	Research funding	
	Other	
	Unclear	
Other		
	Add	
	Unclear	

V. Intervention type

Behavioural interventions	
Dietary interventions and nutrition	
Digital health interventions	
Population-level interventions	Public health
Screening intervention (early detection)	
Vaccines	
Vector control	
Pharmacological intervention	
Procedures	
Surgery	
Psychology	
Physical activity	
Physical therapy	
Physiotherapy	
Policy or programme	
Traditional, complementary and integrative medicine	
Other	

VI. Intersectionality

Intersectionality		
Mark if there is a focus on the following groups		
Ethnicity, race or ancestry groups		
	Yes	
	No	
	Unclear	
	Ethnicity	
	Add	
	Add	
	Race	
	Add	
	Add	
	Ancestry groups	
	Add	
	Add	
	Reporting	
	Reported	
	Reported but unclear	
	Not reported	
	Handling by reviewers	
	As reported by the authors	
	Assumed by the reviewers	

	Corrected by the reviewers	
Qualifications and education		
	Yes	
	No	
	Unclear	
Qualifications and Education		
	Add	
	Add	
Reporting		
	Reported	
	Reported but unclear	
	Not reported	
Handling by reviewers		
	As reported by the authors	
	Assumed by the reviewers	
	Corrected by the reviewers	
Income and wealth		
	Yes	
	No	
	Unclear	
Income and wealth		
	Add	
	Add	
Reporting		
	Reported	
	Reported but unclear	
	Not reported	
Handling by reviewers		
	As reported by the authors	
	Assumed by the reviewers	
	Corrected by the reviewers	
Employment and occupation		
	Yes	
	No	
	Unclear	
Employment and occupation		
	Add	
	Add	
Reporting		
	Reported	
	Reported but unclear	
	Not reported	
Handling by reviewers		
	As reported by the authors	
	Assumed by the reviewers	
	Corrected by the reviewers	
Underserved area		
	Yes	
	No	
	Unclear	
Underserved area		
	Add	
	Add	
Reporting		
	Reported	

	Reported but unclear	
	Not reported	
	Handling by reviewers	
	As reported by the authors	
	Assumed by the reviewers	
	Corrected by the reviewers	
Age		
Source: Mesh terms for age groups ¹¹⁰		
	Yes	
	No	
	Unclear	
	Age	
	Newborn	
	Infant	
	Child	
	Adolescent	
	Young adult	
	Middle aged adult	
	Aged 80 or over	
	Frail elderly	
	Reporting	
	Reported	
	Reported but unclear	
	Not reported	
	Handling by reviewers	
	As reported by the authors	
	Assumed by the reviewers	
	Corrected by the reviewers	
Language		
	Yes	
	No	
	Unclear	
	Language	
	Add	
	Add	
	Reporting	
	Reported	
	Reported but unclear	
	Not reported	
	Handling by reviewers	
	As reported by the authors	
	Assumed by the reviewers	
	Corrected by the reviewers	
Religion		
	Yes	
	No	
	Unclear	
	Religion	
	Add	
	Reporting	
	Reported	
	Reported but unclear	
	Not reported	
	Handling by reviewers	
	As reported by the authors	
	Assumed by the reviewers	

	Corrected by the reviewers	
Disability (physical, mental and learning disabilities)		
	Yes	
	No	
	Unclear	
Disability		
	Add	
Reporting		
	Reported	
	Reported but unclear	
	Not reported	
Handling by reviewers		
	As reported by the authors	
	Assumed by the reviewers	
	Corrected by the reviewers	
Underrepresented groups		
	Yes	
	No	
	Unclear	
Reporting		
	Reported	
	Reported but unclear	
	Not reported	
Handling by reviewers		
	As reported by the authors	
	Assumed by the reviewers	
	Corrected by the reviewers	
Multiple disadvantage groups		
	Yes	
	No	
	Unclear	
Reporting		
	Reported	
	Reported but unclear	
	Not reported	
Handling by reviewers		
	As reported by the authors	
	Assumed by the reviewers	
	Corrected by the reviewers	

VII. Approach used to consider intersectionality

Approach used to address intersectionality		
	Stratified analysis	
	Subgroup analyses	
	Meta-regression	
	Other	

VIII. Differences in outcomes by sex/gender

Differences by sex		
	Found	
	Not found	
	Unclear	
	Not applicable	

	Reporting	
	Reported	
	Reported but unclear	
	Not reported	
	Handling by reviewers	
	As reported by the authors	
	Assumed by the reviewers	
	Corrected by the reviewers	
Differences by gender		
	Found	
	Not found	
	Unclear	
	Not applicable	
	Reporting	
	Reported	
	Reported but unclear	
	Not reported	
	Handling by reviewers	
	As reported by the authors	
	Assumed by the reviewers	
	Corrected by the reviewers	

IX. Publication characteristics

Publication characteristics		
Open access		
	Available	
	Not available	
Publication year		
	Add	
	2020	
	2021	
	2022	
	2023	
	2024	
	2025	
Journal name		
	BMJ	
	
Contact author's region		
Source: United Nations, Statistics Division https://ourworldindata.org/grapher/world-regions-un2		
Africa		
	Northern Africa (UN M49)	
Americas		
Asia		

	Europe	
	Oceania	
	Antarctica	
First and contact author's country		
To import from <i>EPPI-Reviewer</i> shareable codesets		
	Spain	
	Add	
Funding agency		
	Pharmaceutical company	
	Tobacco company	
	Governmental organisation	
	Australian Agency for International Development	
	DFID (UK Department for International Development)	
	CDC (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention)	
	International organisation	
	GAIN (Global Alliance for Improved Nutrition)	
	UNICEF	
	World Bank	
	WHO	
	Add	
	Research institution	
	The Institute for International and Economic Policy	
	Foundations	
	Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation	

X. Evidence synthesis characteristics

1. Evidence synthesis type		
	Systematic review	
	Prevalence or incidence	
	Aetiology or risk factor	
	Diagnostic test accuracy	
	Prognosis: overall prognosis research	
	Prognostic factor research	
	Prognostic model research	
	Predictors of treatment effect	
	Interventions	
	Burden of illness studies or monetary cost studies	
	Economic evaluation studies	
	Expert opinion and policy analysis SR	

	Psychometric SR	
	Methodology SR	
	Qualitative review	
	Mixed methods review	
	Overviews of reviews	
	Big picture review	
	Scoping review	
	Mapping reviews and “Evidence and Gap Maps”	
	Other	
	Unclear	
	Not applicable	
	Reporting	
	Reported	
	Reported but unclear	
	Not reported	
	Handling by reviewers	
	As reported by the authors	
	Assumed by the reviewers	
	Corrected by the reviewers	
	2. Evidence synthesis mode	
	Standard evidence synthesis	
	Rapid review mode	
	Living review mode	
	Other	
	Unclear	
	Not applicable	
	Reporting	
	Reported	
	Reported but unclear	
	Not reported	
	Handling by reviewers	
	As reported by the authors	
	Assumed by the reviewers	
	Corrected by the reviewers	
	3. Protocol registration date	
	Add date	
	Unclear	
	Not applicable- No protocol found	
	Reporting	
	Reported	
	Reported but unclear	
	Not reported	
	Handling by reviewers	
	As reported by the authors	
	Assumed by the reviewers	
	Corrected by the reviewers	
	4. Protocol registration before starting data extraction	
	Yes	
	No	
	Unclear	
	Not applicable - No protocol found	
	5. Databases searched	
	More than one	
	Grey literature was searched	
	Medline	

	Embase	
	CINAHL	
	...	
	Unclear	
	Not applicable	
	Reporting	
	Reported	
	Reported but unclear	
	Not reported	
	Handling by reviewers	
	As reported by the authors	
	Assumed by the reviewers	
	Corrected by the reviewers	
	6. Assessment of the scientific quality or risk of bias of the included studies	
	Cochrane RoB tool	
	Cochrane RoB2 tool	
	Detail	
	Unclear	
	Not applicable	
	Reporting	
	Reported	
	Reported but unclear	
	Not reported	
	Handling by reviewers	
	As reported by the authors	
	Assumed by the reviewers	
	Corrected by the reviewers	
	7. Assessment of the certainty of the evidence	
	GRADE	
	GRADE-CERQual	
	xxx	
	xxx	
	Unclear	
	Not applicable	
	Reporting	
	Reported	
	Reported but unclear	
	Not reported	
	Handling by reviewers	
	As reported by the authors	
	Assumed by the reviewers	
	Corrected by the reviewers	